

THE POTENTIAL LEVEL OF THE ILAGAN DIOCESAN SCHOOLS SYSTEM BASED ON THE CRITERIA OF ACCREDITATION: A BASIS FOR INSTITUTIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLAN

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to assess the potential level of the Ilagan Diocesan School System based on the criteria of accreditation, with the goal of developing an institutional development plan. Quality education is a basic right enshrined in the Philippine Constitution and mandated by various laws and programs, including the Education Act of 1982, the 1987 Philippine Constitution, and the Government Assistance for Students and Teachers (GASTPE) program. Schools play a vital role in the development of citizens' intellectual, political, social, and economic well-being, and are responsible for delivering quality education. However, quality education remains a challenge in the Philippines. Accreditation has been identified as a means of ensuring quality education, with the evolution of accreditation in the country being characterized by several aborted starts and setbacks. This study builds on previous research that highlights schools' responsibility to pursue and deliver quality education. The government has implemented various initiatives such as the Education for All (EFA) program, the Kinder Basic Education Act, and the enhanced Basic Education Act (K-to-12 Curriculum) to improve the quality of education in the country. The findings of this study contribute to the development of an institutional plan aimed at enhancing the quality of education provided by the Ilagan Diocesan Schools System.

Keywords: *Accreditation, Quality Education, Institutional Development Plan, Philippine Education, School Improvement Plan*

INTRODUCTION

Every citizen has the right to provide a quality education. This is our basic right and, at the same time, a constitutional right. As a basic right, every man has the right to education, to have the capacity to elevate him from poverty, and to fully enjoy life itself in a fast-changing world. This is a constitutional right because it has now been enshrined in the New Constitution. The right is now made explicit or categorical, and it is not just the right to education but the right to quality education at all levels – elementary, high school and collegiate, public and private—and the right to have access to it.

The 1982 Education Act mandates that schools deliver quality education. Chapter II Declaration of Basic State Policy and objectives stipulated that “State shall promote the right of every individual to relevant quality education regardless of sex, age, creed, socio – economic status, physical and mental conditions, racial or ethnic origin, political and other affiliation. The state shall therefore promote and maintain equality of access to education by all its citizens”. In the 1987 Philippine Constitution of Hector S. De Leon Article XIV Section 1, it states that “The State shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all.”

Education refers to the process of training an individual's physical, mental, and/or moral faculties. The overall purpose of education is to provide an individual with knowledge, skills, competence, or desirable qualities of behavior and character to render him fit for the duties of life. This term is also used to refer to the knowledge, skills, or values gained through this process. Therefore, schools play a vital role in the development of the intellectual, political, social, and economic well-being of citizens. Consequently, schools should meet all the requirements to address the needs of people. As the first and foremost social institution, a school has the primary function of moving young people into mainstream society. However, they are not only mandated by the Constitution to educate citizens, but also provide quality education to all.

For Filipinos, high-quality education remains an unattained aspiration that is a significant national issue. The accreditation movement in the Philippines has been largely influenced by the challenges in ensuring workplace readiness and educational quality. It is crucial to continuously monitor the equilibrium among governmental regulations, accreditation led by the private sector, and adaptation to current workplace requirements. Numerous initiatives have been undertaken to establish quality education accreditation. Although the development of accreditation in the Philippines began early, it was marked by several false starts and obstacles caused by stakeholders with conflicting goals and limitations throughout its progression. According to Claravall's 2015 study, "Continuing Search for Quality through Accreditation as Basis for a School Improvement Plan (SIP)," educational institutions are responsible for pursuing and delivering quality education, as well as developing an individual's physical, mental, and moral capacities. Education aims to equip individuals with knowledge, skills, competence, or desirable qualities of behavior and character, preparing them for life responsibilities.

In 1972, the Presidential Commission to Survey Philippine Education (PCSPE) submitted policy recommendations for improving and strengthening higher education. Among others, it recommended that schools be encouraged to join or organize accrediting associations and that a Federation of Accrediting Agencies (FAAP) be established. The Commission Report, known as the Integrated Reorganization Plan (IRP), was approved by President Marcos in his PD201, and subsequently issued Presidential Decrees 6-A, otherwise known as the Educational Development Act of 1972, making accreditation one of the means of upgrading standards of education in the Philippines and providing therein a program of financial assistance.

Several laws and programs of the government mandate both private and public schools to promote quality education. The Government Assistance for Students and Teachers (GASTPE) program, known as the GASTPE Law or RA 6728, Section 2 Declaration of Policy provides the state to promote quality education accessible to all Filipino citizens. Laws and regulations have been issued to articulate the government's accreditation policy. Batas Pambansa 232; RA 7722, Creating the Commission on Higher Education (CHED); CHED Order 1, s.2005 and the 2008 Manual of Regulations for Private Schools, have stipulated voluntary accreditation as a means of ensuring quality education. The state should provide a mechanism to improve the quality of private education by maximizing the use of existing resources.

The Government Education for all (EFA) programs also aim to improve all aspects of the quality of education, particularly in literacy and numeracy skills, which are essential in life. The Kinder Basic Education Act No. 10157 and the enhanced Basic Education Act No. 10533 in February 2012 and May 2012, also known as the K-to-12 Curriculum, which is now fully implemented, is one of the greatest contributions of the Aquino Administration through Bro. Arwin Luistro, the Education Secretary in their pursuit to a globally competitive education system and as compliance to ASEAN Integration/ ASEAN 2015. According to UNESCO, education cannot be achieved without improving quality. In the Philippines and throughout the world, the accepted measure of quality assurance in education is voluntary accreditation.

Accreditation is a complex and challenging task. It affects a wide range of institutional practices, including classroom instruction, capital resources, finances, staffing needs, student services, research, extension programs, administration, and professional development. It is a deliberate and thorough process that is entered into voluntarily for quality assurance and institutional enhancement. Accrediting agencies assess compliance with published administrative and academic standards and seek continuous striving for excellence from the institutions they accredit. As such, accrediting agencies serve students, society, basic and higher education, as well as their accredited institutions and entities, by striving to ensure academic excellence and ethical standards.

The Education Act of 1992 Rule IV of the implementing rules and regulations (IRR) outlined seven provisions governing quality accreditation policy: definition, eligibility for voluntary accreditation, benefits of voluntary accreditation, recognition of private voluntary accrediting associations, accrediting agencies, and lifespan deregulated status.

Hence, private voluntary accreditation provides an opportunity for educational institutions to attain standards above those prescribed as minimum requirements by the government. In this context, the researcher would like to study the potential level of Diocesan Schools in their basic education based on the PAASCU accreditation criteria as a basis for institutional development plans.

There are six (6) identified Diocesan Schools in Isabela, as follows. 1) St. John Berchmans High School, Inc., Cordon Isabela; 2) School of Saint James Apostle, Santiago City; and 3) School of St. Joseph the Worker, Inc, Echague, Isabela; 4) School of Our Lady of Atocha, Inc, Alicia, Isabela; 5) School of Saint Joseph, Inc, Naguilan, Isabela; 6) School of Saint Mathias, Inc, Tumauni, Isabela. The potential level of the Diocesan Schools should be assessed by the employees, students, and parents based on the criteria of accreditation. This will be the basis for formulating an institutional development plan for Diocesan School. The researcher will use the accreditation criteria of PAASCU in her study because this is the accrediting agency that accredited the OLPC High School Department, Level II Reaccredited status, and a former member of the Isabela Diocesan Schools System.

The Philippine Accrediting Association of Schools, Colleges, and Universities (PAASCU) as an accrediting agency has been very helpful to schools that are willing to undergo accreditation for improvement and development and for the delivery of quality education. The PAASCU was established 55 years ago by 11 Catholic schools in the Philippines. Today, PAASCU has 449 member schools, not all of which are Catholic or in the Philippines. Among the strengths of PAASCU that its president, Joel Tabora, S.J., highlighted in his speech at its General Assembly last Nov. 23, 2015, is its international recognition. PAASCU is not only recognized and known in the Philippines but also abroad in terms of its objectives of continuing evaluations for quality assurance. Because of the extremely stringent process that PAASCU uses, schools not only have to show that they are excellent in all areas of education, but they also must show that they have maintained this excellence throughout the years. One example in the province is OLPC, the High School Department. PAASCU, like other internationally recognized accrediting associations, checks whether a school is true to its mission and vision. PAASCU examines both what the school offers to its students (sometimes called “inputs”) and what its students manage to do or become after having gone through the school (sometimes called “outcomes”).

PAASCU accreditation, in effect, assures quality. In business terms, accreditation would be a “quality seal” or “quality certification.” As defined on wisegeek.com, “quality assurance (QA) is a process-centered approach that ensures that a company or organization is providing the best possible products or services. This is related to quality control, which focuses on the results such as testing a sample of items from a batch after production. Although these terms are sometimes used interchangeably, quality assurance focuses on enhancing and improving the process used to create the result, rather than focusing on the result itself. Among the parts of the process that are considered in QA are planning, design, development, production, and service.”

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the potential level of Diocesan Schools based on assessments by parents, students, and employees using accreditation criteria. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions.

1. What is the status of Diocesan Schools as assessed by parents, students, and employees using the criteria for accreditation? Purposes and Objectives Faculty Curricular Programs and Instruction Library/ Instructional Media Center Laboratories Physical Plant and Facilities Student Personnel Services Social Orientation and Community Involvement Organization and Administration
2. Is there a significant difference in the assessment among the students, parents and employees based on the following areas: Purposes and Objectives Faculty Curricular Programs and Instruction Library Laboratories Physical Plant and Facilities Student Personnel Services Social Orientation and Community Involvement Organization and Administration

Hypothesis

There was no significant difference in the assessment among parents, students, and employees on the potential level of the diocesan schools based on accreditation criteria.

METHODOLOGY

Research Method

The researcher utilized a descriptive evaluative method to assess diocesan schools in Isabela according to accreditation criteria, forming the basis for an institutional development plan. Calmorin et al. (2007) stated that the descriptive survey method is suitable when subjects vary, aiming to understand the extent of the different conditions. The term survey refers to data collection on current conditions, which is useful for providing factual value and highlighting key aspects.

Selection and Descriptions of Respondents

The study respondents were parents, students, and employees of six (6) Diocesan schools in Isabela: St. John Berchman High School, Inc. Cordon, Isabela, St. St., and St. St. James the Apostle, Inc., Santiago City, School of St. Joseph, the Worker Inc., Echague, Isabela, School of Our Lady of Atocha, Inc., Alicia, Isabela, School of Saint Joseph, Inc., Naguilian, Isabela, School of Saint Matthias, Inc., Tumauni, Isabela

The student respondents from each school were chosen randomly. The employee respondents included all faculty, administrators, and non-teaching staff. For parent respondents, all General PTCA officers were chosen as respondents, including the president of each Home-Room officer.

Frequency Distribution of Respondents

Diocesan Schools	Student-Respondents	Employee-Respondents	Parent-Respondents
St. John Berchman High School, Inc., Cordon, Isabela	100	32	30
School of St. James the Apostle, Inc., Santiago City, Isabela	100	26	30
School of St. Joseph the Worker, Inc., Echague, Isabela	100	49	60
School of Our Lady of Atocha, Inc., Alicia, Isabela	100	53	60
School of Saint Joseph, Inc., Naguilian, Isabela	100	16	30
School of Saint Matthias, Inc., Tumauni, Isabela	100	22	30

The table displays the frequency distribution of the respondents. The randomly chosen student respondents included 25 individuals from each academic year (first through fourth years). Employee respondents included all teaching and non-teaching staff, including principals and chaplains. The parent respondents were all General PTCA officers.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought permission from the Superintendent of the Ilagan Diocesan School System (IDSS) to distribute the questionnaire and coordinate with the chaplain and principal of each diocesan school. With the Superintendent's approval, a meeting was convened with the faculty, principal, and chaplain to discuss the research objectives and enlist their help in distributing and retrieving the questionnaires. During the meeting, the researcher explained that the study aimed to evaluate the potential level of Diocesan Schools based on accreditation criteria to formulate institutional development plans. The researcher distributed, retrieved, and reviewed all questionnaires with the class adviser's assistance in distributing the questionnaires to parent respondents.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The Weighted Mean method was utilized to determine the potential caliber of Diocesan Schools, based on accreditation criteria as evaluated by students, parents, and staff members. ANOVA was employed to investigate whether significant variations existed in the assessments provided by students, parents, and employees regarding accreditation areas.

Data Analysis Procedure

The Rating Scale used by PAASCU (www.PAASCU.com) will be the basis for the respondent's assessment of the potential level of the Diocesan Schools by the parent respondents, employees, and students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

What is the status of Diocesan Schools assessed by parents, students, and employees using the criteria of accreditation?

Table 1 The Status of the Diocesan Schools on the Area of Purposes and Objectives as Assessed by the Parent – Respondents

PURPOSES AND OBJECTIVES	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBHS	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The school's philosophy, vision, and mission are clearly stated.	3.03	Good	3.06	Good	3.1	Good	3.11	Good	3.26	Good	3.03	Good
The philosophy, vision, mission are reflective of the school's identity and core values.	3.6	Very Good	3.9	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.7	Very Good
The mission statement of the school clearly communicates: A. A culture of excellence	3.5	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.6	Very Good
B. Realistic and achievable educational goals for the students.	3.7	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.73	Very Good
The mission statement deals with the role of the school in: The community	3.53	Very Good	3.33	Good	3.53	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.33	Good	3.53	Very Good
B. Philippine society	3.63	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.71	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.73	Very Good
C. Global society	3.36	Good	3.2	Good	3.46	Very Good	3.48	Very Good	3.2	Good	3.46	Very Good
The objectives clearly articulate the <u>schools</u> philosophy, vision, and mission.	3.53	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.8	Very Good
The objectives are clear, specific and attainable.	3.5	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
The objectives are suited to the clientele which the school intends to serve.	3.6	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.63	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.66	Very Good
These objectives are periodically reviewed and updated.	3.7	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.8	Very Good	3.18	Good	3.06	Good	3.86	Very Good
The different sectors of the school are consulted in the review of the philosophy, vision, mission and objectives.	3.53	Very Good	3.87	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.63	Very Good	3.63	Very Good	3.66	Very Good

The philosophy, vision, and mission, as well as the objectives are published in a bulletin of information.	3.53	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.87	Very Good	3.63	Very Good	3.5	Very Good
The school includes among its objectives a well integrated program for the intellectuals, moral, social, emotional, spiritual, and physical development of its students.	3.5	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.06	Good	3.56	Very Good	3.63	Very Good
The objectives of the school are in accordance with the educational aims of: A. The institution to which it is affiliated	3.14	Good	3.16	Good	3.43	Very Good	3.14	Good	3.6	Very Good	3.46	Very Good
B. The department of education.	3.26	Good	3.36	Good	3.26	Good	3.25	Good	3.43	Very Good	3.2	Good
The objectives are in consonance with the following rational development goals: A. Patriotism and love of country	3.4	Very Good	3.3	Good	3.53	Very Good	3.33	Good	3.6	Very Good	3.53	Very Good
B. Respect for human rights	3.53	Very Good	3.83	Very Good	3.83	Very Good	3.83	Very Good	3.2	Good	3.86	Very Good
C. Economic self sufficiency	3.33	Good	3.13	Good	3.46	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.46	Very Good
D. Cultural enrichment	3.66	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.7	Very Good
E. Social Responsibility	3.34	Good	3.5	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.41	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.46	Very Good
F. Development of moral character and personal discipline	3.83	Very Good	3.86	Very Good	3.93	Very Good	3.91	Very Good	3.83	Very Good	3.93	Very Good
G. Scientific and technological knowledge	3.33	Good	3.56	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.12	Good	3.16	Good	3.46	Very Good
H. Environmental consciousness and responsibility	3.76	Very Good	3.08	Good	3.93	Very Good	3.22	Good	3.7	Very Good	3.86	Very Good
The faculty members and other school personnel understand and accept the schools' philosophy, vision, mission and objectives.	3.23	Good	3.26	Good	3.3	Good	3.3	Good	3.26	Good	3.3	Good
The faculty and other personnel are informed of the philosophy, vision, mission and objectives of the school.	3.5	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3.55	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
The parents understand and accept the school's philosophy, vision, mission and objectives.	3.33	Good	3.53	Very Good	3.97	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.9	Very Good	3.8	Very Good
Mean Average	3.48	Very Good	3.50	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.50	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.59	Very Good

The data revealed that five of the six Diocesan Schools received a Very Good rating for their purpose and objectives, with mean scores ranging from 3.49 to 3.60. These institutions: St. Joseph in Naguilan, Our Lady of Atocha in Alicia, Saint Joseph the Worker in Echague, St. James the Apostle in Santiago City, and Saint Joseph Berchmans High

School in Cordon—demonstrated moderately extensive and functional provisions. In contrast, Saint Matthias in Tumauni and Isabela earned a good rating with a mean of 3.47, indicating an adequate and well-functioning purpose and objective provisions. The accreditation criteria show that these educational institutions have established their purposes and objectives for student admission and instruction, striving for a comprehensive program that integrates intellectual, moral, social, cultural, and physical development.

Table 2 The Status of the Diocesan Schools on the Area of Faculty as Assessed by the Parent – Respondents

FACULTY	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
There is a published policy establishing faculty selection procedures	3.2	Good	3.25	Good	2.8	Good	2.82	Good	3.9	Very Good	2.77	Good
The process of selection includes: A. An evaluation of the applicants' transcript of records and other credentials.	3.57	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.51	Very Good	2.51	Fair
B. Oral writing interviews	3.32	Good	4	Very Good	3.28	Good	3.32	Good	3.38	Good	3.32	Good
C. Qualifying tests	3.32	Good	3.75	Very Good	3.34	Good	3.34	Good	3.29	Good	3.32	Good
D. Classroom demonstration	3.45	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.45	Very Good	3.45	Very Good	3.38	Good	3.54	Very Good
E. Consideration of recommendations from reliable sources	3.64	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.51	Very Good	3.64	Very Good
F. Medical examination	3.58	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.58	Very Good
The selection of teachers is a process involving A. Principal	3.51	Very Good	3.87	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.51	Very Good
B. Assistant Principal / Academic in charge	3.91	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.93	Very Good
C. Subject Area Coordinators	3.61	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.47	Very Good	3.47	Very Good	3.58	Very Good	3.61	Very Good
D. Others: Some teachers are involved Human Resource Personnel	3.41	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.37	Good	3.27	Good	3.48	Very Good	3.41	Very Good
In the selection of faculty members, the following are considered: A. Professional competence	3.67	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.55	Very Good	3.55	Very Good	3.8	Very Good	3.67	Very Good
B. Personality in relation to teaching	3.61	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.45	Very Good	3.45	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.61	Very Good
The school's specific policies for selection of faculty members are observed.	3.61	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.58	Very Good	3.61	Very Good
The stated procedures for selecting faculty members are satisfactory.	3.93	Very Good	3.87	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	3.93	Very Good	3.93	Very Good
The procedures of selecting faculty members are consistent	3.63	Very Good	3.25	Good	3.41	Very Good	3.41	Very Good	3.58	Very Good	3.67	Very Good

The methods in selecting competent faculty member have been successful.	3.54	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	3.27	Good	3.27	Good	3.45	Very Good	3.54	Very Good
The percentage of fully qualified members of the faculty is satisfactory.	3.32	Good	3.43	Very Good	4.16	Very Good	4.16	Very Good	3.89	Very Good	4.32	Exc.
The percentage of the faculty members with academic preparation beyond the minimum degree requirements is satisfactory.	3.54	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	3.96	Very Good	3.96	Very Good	2.67	Good	4.29	Exc.
The preparation of the faculty as a whole to the requirements of the curriculum is well watched.	2.67	Good	3.13	Good	4.04	Very Good	4.04	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	4.25	Exc.
The total teaching experience of the faculty is satisfactory.	4	Very Good	4	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.96	Very Good	4	Very Good
The faculty members' length of service in the school is satisfactory	2.3	Fair	3.81	Very Good	3.91	Very Good	3.91	Very Good	3.12	Good	4.16	Very Good
There are an adequate number of faculties in relation to the educational program and to the philosophy, vision, mission and objectives of the school.	2.1	Fair	3.06	Good	3.96	Very Good	3.96	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	4.19	Very Good
Mean Average	3.41	Very Good	3.60	Very Good	3.58	Very Good	3.58	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.67	Very Good

The data show that all Diocesan Schools were generally rated Very Good in the faculty area, indicating moderately extensive and well-functioning provisions. According to the PAASCU accreditation criteria, a competent faculty member is crucial for a good school. Such a faculty is not just a group of skilled teachers, but a collaborative unit with shared educational goals, driven by a clear philosophy, vision, mission, and objectives. The faculty is the school's backbone and should be motivated, dedicated, and academically and professionally competent. Therefore, they should attend more seminars and training courses to enhance their effectiveness and efficiency.

Table 3 The Status of the Diocesan Schools on the Area of Curricular Programs and Instruction as Assessed by the Parent – Respondents

INSTRUCTION	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The curriculum complies the learning competence of the Basic Education Curriculum (Deped)	2.86	Good	3.18	Good	3.98	Very Good	3.86	Very Good	3.83	Very Good	3.96	Very Good
The curriculum supports the school's philosophy, vision, mission, and objectives.	2.26	Fair	3.62	Very Good	3.26	Good	3.26	Good	3.36	Good	3.26	Good
There is evidence of remote and immediate preparation and thorough planning of instructional activities	3.13	Good	4.06	Very Good	4.12	Very Good	3.11	Good	3.78	Very Good	4.35	Exc.

Instructional activities show systematic organization, implementation and evaluation.	3.03	Good	3.68	Very Good	4.43	Exc.	4.23	Exc.	3.98	Very Good	3.76	Very Good
Opportunities are provided for the application of skills/ concepts learned.	3.03	Good	3.68	Very Good	3.05	Good	4.54	Exc.	3.56	Very Good	3.06	Good
Methods and technique used instruction as varied, current, relevant and creative.	3.46	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	4.23	Excellent	3.43	Very Good
There is a pertinent use of the medium of Instruction.	3.46	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	4.35	Exc.	3.46	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.43	Very Good
Activities are provided to develop leadership and followership ability.	3.4	Very Good	3.1	Good	3.43	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	4.32	Exc.
A learning atmosphere is maintained in all classes through sound classroom management.	3.83	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.9	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
Students participate actively in class.	3.36	Good	3.68	Very Good	3.35	Good	3.35	Good	4.2	Exc.	4.23	Exc.
Students accomplish assigned tasks and homework.	3.13	Good	3.58	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	4.45	Exc.	3.16	Good
Students show positive values and attitudes in and out of the classroom.	3.4	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	3.89	Very Good	3.4	Very Good	3.36	Good	3.36	Good
Students show ability to apply the skills and knowledge they have learned on the classroom.	3.23	Good	3.56	Very Good	4.36	Exc.	3.23	Good	3.29	Good	3.26	Good
Examination is couched and returned to the students on time.	3.26	Good	3.68	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.28	Good	3.33	Good	3.36	Good
The grading system is well-defined and reflects the students' performance.	3.5	Very Good	3.87	Very Good	3.48	Very Good	3.48	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
The administration has regular supervisory visits to classes and posts an observation conferences.	3.23	Good	3.18	Good	3.98	Very Good	3.31	Good	3.45	Very Good	3.33	Good
The administration employs concrete measures to ensure that rules concerning students' class attendance and punctuality are followed.	3.23	Good	3.68	Very Good	3.25	Good	4.33	Exc.	3.16	Good	4.33	Exc.
The administration requires the use of instructional materials, devices and equipment.	3.6	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	4.2	Exc.	3.63	Very Good	3.6	Very Good
Measured are to ensure the punctuality and regular attendance of faculty members at their schedule of classes.	3.6	Very Good	3.87	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.89	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.6	Very Good
Records of the daily attendance of students are maintained.	3.53	Very Good	3.37	Good	3.51	Very Good	3.51	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.53	Very Good
Mean Average	3.27	Good	3.60	Very Good	3.72	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.62	Very Good

The data indicate that five out of six Diocesan Schools were rated very good in Instruction, implying moderately extensive and effective instructional provision at the School of Saint Joseph, Naguilan; School of Our Lady of Atocha, Alicia; School of Saint Joseph the Worker, Echague; and School of St. James the Apostle, Santiago City; and St. John Berchmans High School, Cordon Isabela. The School of St. Tumauni were rated good with a mean of 3.27, suggesting adequate and well-functioning instruction.

Claravall (2015) asserted that the instructional process is crucial for realizing the potential of students. Quality instruction manifests itself in the curriculum, teaching methods, classroom management, and students' academic performance. Schools should prioritize and continuously improve instructional quality, focusing on both vertical and horizontal subjects and grade articulation. Effective classroom management and positive values should be integrated into learning. Examinations and tests should be used strategically, with regular analyses to identify student strengths and weaknesses and to evaluate teaching effectiveness and student progress. Anselmo (2024) stressed the need to support out-of-field teachers with adequate resources to ensure effective instruction aligned with curriculum standards.

Table 4 shows the potential level of the Diocesan Schools as assessed by the parent respondents in the library area.

LIBRARY	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The library is administered by a qualified and licensed librarian.	2.11	Fair	2.37	Fair	2.76	Good	2.33	Fair	2.76	Good	3.35	Good
There is a provision for clerical assistance.	2.13	Fair	2.31	Fair	2.26	Fair	3.26	Good	3.42	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
The number of librarians and clerical assistants is adequate.	2.45	Fair	2.18	Fair	3.3	Good	3.3	Good	3.23	Good	3.43	Very Good
The librarian has faculty status.	2.34	Fair	2.25	Fair	3.03	Good	3.03	Good	3.18	Good	3.78	Very Good
The librarian participates regularly in faculty meetings and other faculty committee meetings.	2.17	Fair	2.12	Fair	3.06	Good	3.06	Good	3.56	Very Good	3.17	Good
Provision is made for the professional growth of the library and AV personnel.	2.12	Fair	2.43	Fair	3.36	Good	3.36	Good	3.45	Very Good	3.45	Very Good
The audio-visual or non-print resources are administered by trained audio-visual personnel.	2.13	Fair	2.43	Fair	3.43	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.43	Very Good
The number of clerical / technical assistant is adequate.	2.16	Fair	2.75	Good	3.73	Very Good	3.13	Good	3.12	Good	3.46	Very Good
There is an adequate professional preparation of the librarians and other audio-visual personnel.	2.78	Good	2.13	Fair	4.2	Excellent	3.2	Good	3.23	Good	3.9	Very Good

The librarians and audio-visual personnel are professionally updated.	2.35	Fair	2.62	Good	3.46	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.34	Good	2.3	Fair
There is an adequate number of librarians / staff	2.13	Fair	2.31	Fair	3.3	Good	3.3	Good	3.33	Good	3.84	Very Good
There is an adequate number of audio-visual personnel /or staff.	2.43	Fair	2.31	Fair	3.6	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.45	Very Good	3.87	Very Good
There is an satisfactory participation of the library and audio-visual center personnel in the development of the educational program.	2.65	Good	2.25	Fair	3.3	Good	3.3	Good	3.31	Good	3.59	Very Good
The school formulates a well-prepared budget for the library and A.V Center	2.89	Good	2.62	Good	3.26	Good	3.26	Good	3.13	Good	3.59	Very Good
The librarian participates in the preparation and management of the budget.	2.43	Fair	2.12	Fair	3.56	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	2.34	Fair
There is a systematic record keeping procedure for the library and A.V Center.	2.54	Fair	2.62	Good	3.03	Good	3.03	Good	3.22	Good	3.34	Good
There is an existing library/ audio-visual program for the school.	2.44	Fair	2.31	Fair	3.03	Good	3.03	Good	3.55	Very Good	3.4	Very Good
There are basic tools and policies for the selection and purchase of print and non-print materials.	2.32	Fair	2.81	Good	3.8	Very Good	3.8	Very Good	3.22	Good	3.71	Very Good
Print and non-print holdings are well balance.	2.22	Fair	2.18	Fair	3.83	Very Good	3.83	Very Good	3.21	Good	3.2	Good
Collection of print and non-print materials is evaluated regularly.	2.56	Fair	2.62	Good	3.56	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.2	Good	3.43	Very Good
Mean Average	2.37	Fair	2.38	Fair	3.40	Good	3.29	Good	3.30	Good	3.41	Very Good

The table indicates that two schools were rated fair, two were rated good, and two were rated very good by the respondents. School of Saint Matthias and the School of St. Joseph have limited but functional libraries. By contrast, the School of Saint Joseph the Worker and the School of Saint James the Apostle have adequate and well-functioning libraries, whereas the libraries at Our Lady of Atocha and the School of St. John Berchmans' High School is moderately extensive and functional. Libraries and audiovisual centers, referred to as Learning Resource Centers (LRC), Educational Media Centers (EMC), Instructional Material Centers (IMC), or Media Centers, are central to a school's instructional program. They serve faculty, students, and administrators by providing access to information, developing research strategies, and using various media.

Each school demonstrated a media center program capable of enhancing instruction and fostering lifelong reading skills (Morris 1992; *Administering School Library Media Center). However, the assessment highlighted areas of improvement, such as the absence of qualified and licensed librarians. Although respondents rated the facilities as fair to good, they might not have been aware of the qualifications of the librarians. Schools should also develop a well-prepared budget for libraries and audio-visual centers, as these are crucial for stimulating independent intellectual development and contributing significantly to students' liberal education.

Table 5 The Status of the Diocesan Schools on the Area of Laboratories as Assessed by the Parent – Respondents

LABORATORY	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
Laboratories are spacious enough for the different activities	2.73	Good	2.16	Fair	2.81	Good	2.18	Fair	2.8	Good	2.73	Good
Laboratories are appropriately designed for each science subject.	3	Good	2.62	Good	3.01	Good	2.01	Fair	3.06	Good	3.1	Good
Laboratories are accessible to students.	2.13	Fair	2.06	Fair	3.16	Good	3.16	Good	2.18	Fair	3.3	Good
A separate storage space under lock and key is provided for poisonous chemicals.	2.76	Good	2.17	Fair	2.92	Good	3.75	Very Good	2.83	Good	3.76	Very Good
Preventive measures are taken against danger or discomfort from noxious or unpleasant cases.	2.63	Good	2.19	Fair	2.75	Good	3.7	Very Good	3.17	Good	3.63	Very Good
The <u>equipment</u> tools and supplies are sufficient to enable the students to work in small groups.	2.9	Good	2.17	Fair	3.7	Very Good	2.88	Good	3.3	Good	3.9	Very Good
Trained laboratory assistants or technicians are employed.	2.8	Good	2.43	Fair	3.88	Very Good	3.85	Very Good	3.9	Very Good	3.8	Very Good
The laboratory assistant or technicians is skilled and capable of doing minor repairs of laboratory apparatus and equipment.	2.73	Good	2.06	Fair	3.85	Very Good	2.73	Good	3.8	Very Good	2.7	Good
Equipment, apparatus and supplies are systematically stored.	2.4	Fair	2.16	Fair	2.98	Good	3.43	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.4	Very Good
Materials and supplies are properly labeled.	2.1	Fair	2.5	Fair	3.43	Very Good	3.11	Good	3.16	Good	3.1	Good
The laboratories are properly maintained.	2.7	Good	2.18	Fair	3.11	Good	2.11	Fair	2.96	Good	3.9	Very Good
A guide for the use of the laboratory is provided to the students, laboratory staff and faculty.	2.13	Fair	2.87	Good	3.71	Very Good	3.18	Good	3.2	Good	3.3	Good
An organized laboratory orientation program is given to all students.	2.93	Good	3	Good	3.18	Good	2.98	Good	3.93	Very Good	3.93	Very Good
Resources of the community and environment are utilized in laboratory experiments and activities.	2.1	Fair	2.16	Fair	2.98	Good	3.13	Good	3.13	Good	3.1	Good
Procurement and upgrading of equipment and supplies are done periodically.	2.63	Good	2.62	Good	3.13	Good	2.68	Good	2.73	Good	3.63	Very Good
A computer room / laboratory is made available for the computer program.	2.93	Good	2.68	Good	3.68	Very Good	2.9	Good	3.03	Good	3.42	Very Good
The computer room is equipped with enough computers which are properly installed.	2.8	Good	2.06	Fair	2.9	Good	3.75	Very Good	3.86	Very Good	3.8	Very Good

The computer room / laboratory is strategically located.	2.2	Fair	2.93	Good	2.75	Good	3.15	Good	3.3	Good	3.2	Good
The computer room is well lighted, well-ventilated and well maintained.	2.73	Good	2.13	Fair	3.5	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.73	Very Good
There are safety provisions in the computer laboratory.	2.93	Good	2.68	Good	2.23	Fair	2.9	Good	3.2	Good	3.93	Very Good
There is a computer laboratory development program.	2	Fair	2.83	Good	2.9	Good	2.03	Fair	3.06	Good	3.03	Good
Mean Average	2.58	Fair	2.41	Fair	3.27	Good	3.02	Good	3.23	Good	3.39	Good

Respondents from the School of St. Matthias and the School of St. Joseph rated the area as fair (means: 2.58 and 2.41), while those from the School of Our Lady of Atocha, School of St. Joseph the Worker, School of St. James the Apostle, and School of St. John Berchmans High School rated it as good (means: 3.27, 3.02, 3.23, and 3.39). This implies that the former schools have limited functional laboratories, whereas the latter schools have adequate and well-functioning laboratories. Adequate laboratory facilities and equipment, providing sufficient space and suitability for demonstrations, are crucial for effective instruction and alignment with the requirements of Science Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE), and Computer Education Programs. Equipment and supplies met the minimum standards of the Department of Education, ensuring the achievement of specific school objectives. Anselmo et al. (2024) emphasized the importance of examining contemporary pedagogical innovations and digital tool integration, as well as understanding educators' and students' perspectives, to improve teaching strategies and comply with accreditation criteria. Modern learning environments must adapt to technological advancements and instructional innovations to meet evolving educational standards in the context of accreditation and high-quality instruction. This study investigates the impact of these developments on teaching and learning processes that are directly linked to standards of educational excellence in various accreditation frameworks.

Table 6 shows the results of the assessment of the respondents in the areas of physical plants and facilities.

PHYSICAL PLANT	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The campus is accessible to the clientele	2.56	Fair	2.37	Fair	2.63	Good	2.6	Good	2.6	Good	2.96	Good
The size of the campus is adequate to meet the needs of the present school population.	2.46	Fair	2.43	Fair	3.03	Good	2.9	Good	2.9	Good	3.16	Good
The campus is sufficiently free from the pollution	2.76	Good	2.12	Fair	2.86	Good	2.9	Good	2.93	Good	2.96	Good
There are provisions for future expansion.	2.43	Fair	2.31	Fair	2.96	Good	2.86	Good	2.86	Good	3	Good
There is sufficient parking area.	2.7	Good	2.87	Good	3.05	Good	3.21	Good	3.33	Good	2.96	Good
The buildings are reasonably earthquake and fire resistant.	2.26	Fair	2.37	Fair	2.86	Good	2.71	Good	2.73	Good	2.98	Good

Corridors and stairways are wide enough to ensure easy traffic flow.	2.96	Good	2.62	Good	3.1	Good	3.8	Very Good	3.33	Good	3	Good
Corridors and stairways are free from obstructions and stored materials.	2.63	Good	2.43	Fair	2.61	Good	2.56	Fair	2.66	Good	2.93	Good
The school building design provided wide overhanging leaves for air circulation and for safety reasons.	2.93	Good	2.68	Good	3.08	Good	3.15	Good	3.26	Good	2.83	Good
Covered walks protect students during inclement weather.	2.53	Fair	2.62	Good	2.8	Good	2.63	Good	3.66	Very Good	2.76	Good
Sufficient windows provide adequate lighting.	2.43	Fair	2.62	Good	2.68	Good	2.5	Fair	2.5	Fair	2.5	Fair
All classrooms and instruction areas are well ventilated.	2.9	Good	2	Fair	2.96	Good	3	Good	3.13	Good	2.9	Good
The comfort rooms are well ventilated.	2.8	Good	2.68	Good	2.9	Good	2.81	Good	2.8	Good	2.8	Good
The water supply is potable and adequate.	2.76	Good	3.06	Good	2.96	Good	2.91	Good	2.83	Good	2.86	Good
Drinking water is tested periodically.	2.03	Fair	2.93	Good	2.41	Fair	2.08	Fair	2.1	Fair	2.46	Fair
Comfort rooms and laboratory facilities are well maintained	2.4	Fair	2.87	Good	2.9	Good	2.9	Good	2.93	Good	2.86	Good
There is adequate provision for internal and external communication services.	2.83	Good	2.81	Good	2.9	Good	2.83	Good	2.86	Good	2.83	Good
Fire and earthquake drills are conducted periodically.	2.63	Good	2.93	Good	3.06	Good	3.16	Good	3.06	Good	2.96	Good
The various classrooms are functionally planned.	2.93	Good	2.87	Good	2.91	Good	2.86	Good	2.96	Good	2.73	Good
There are provisions for safe entry and waiting in case of emergencies.	2.86	Good	3.06	Good	2.91	Good	2.9	Good	2.9	Good	2.66	Good
Auditorium /gymnasium / covered court is/are accessible and safe.	2.83	Good	2.93	Good	3.28	Good	3.36	Good	3.4	Very Good	2.96	Good
The canteen is large enough to accommodate the students.	2.73	Good	3.12	Good	3.78	Very Good	2.71	Good	3.63	Very Good	2.83	Good
A first-aid room / clinic is available	2.96	Good	3.2	Good	2.9	Good	2.96	Good	2.96	Good	2.9	Good
The offices of the key administrators are accessible to all concerned.	2.86	Good	3.6	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	2.86	Good	2.86	Good	2.86	Good
A private office is provided for the principal.	2.73	Good	3.25	Good	3.75	Very Good	2.71	Good	2.6	Good	2.73	Good
Mean Average	2.68	Good	2.75	Good	3.01	Good	2.87	Good	2.73	Good	2.86	Good

All schools were rated as good by respondents regarding the physical plant, indicating adequate and well-functioning provisions. The table highlights improvement opportunities such as campus size and location, provisions for future expansion, potable and adequate water supply, and periodic testing. However, schools should only offer the facilities necessary for their programmes (PAASCU).

Table 7 The Status of the Diocesan Schools on the Area of Student Personnel Services as Assessed by the Parent – Respondent

STUDENT SERVICES	SSM		SSJ- N		SOLA		SSJ- E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The admission policy is consistent with the philosophy, vision, mission and objective of the school.	2.5	Fair	2.66	Good	3.5	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.36	Good	3.5	Very Good
The objectives of the guidance program are clearly stated.	2.93	Good	2.97	Good	3.83	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.53	Very Good
There is a developmental program for career guidance.	2.17	Fair	3.65	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	3.8	Very Good	3.76	Very Good
The school has an alumni/alumnae association.	2.7	Good	3.56	Very Good	3.86	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.86	Very Good	3.86	Very Good
The health program emphasizes both physical and mental health.	2.8	Good	3	Good	3.67	Very Good	3.89	Very Good	3.96	Very Good	3.86	Very Good
The school has a physician, a nurse and dentist.	2.9	Good	3.18	Good	3.9	Very Good	3.86	Very Good	3.9	Very Good	3.9	Very Good
Medical and dental check-ups of all students are done annually.	2.7	Good	3.8	Very Good	3.93	Very Good	3.9	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.98	Very Good
Hot meals are available in the school canteen/cafeteria	3	Good	2.89	Good	3	Good	2.89	Good	3.51	Very Good	3.76	Very Good
Canteen/ cafeteria prices are reasonable.	2.3	Fair	3.4	Very Good	3.9	Very Good	3.34	Good	3.9	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
Students' participation in the student activity program is properly recorded /documented.	2.9	Good	3.8	Very Good	3.4	Very Good	3.34	Good	3.46	Very Good	3.9	Very Good
Community resources are tapped/utilized to enrich the student activity program.	2.4	Fair	3.2	Good	3.76	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.54	Very Good
The school has specific policies and regulations in the organization and grouping of clubs including the activities.	2.76	Good	3.2	Good	3.89	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	3.76	Very Good
The school facilitates the availability of transportation to students.	2.9	Good	3.34	Good	3.98	Very Good	3.36	Good	3.9	Very Good	3.5	Very Good
A monitoring scheme for student transportation service is observed.	2.4	Fair	3.23	Good	3.76	Very Good	3.9	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.9	Very Good
Community resources are tapped/utilized to enrich the student activity program.	2.76	Good	2.34	Fair	3.88	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.86	Very Good	3.76	Very Good
Mean Average	2.74	Good	3.29	Good	3.70	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.63	Very Good

The table shows respondents' ratings of Student Personnel Services in Six Diocesan Schools. The School of St. Matthias rated good, with a mean of 2.74, indicating adequate and well-functioning services. The School of Our Lady of Atocha (mean of 3.70), School of Joseph the Worker (mean of 3.53), and School of St. James the Apostle (mean of 3.65), and School of St. John Berchmans High School (mean = 3.63) was rated as having moderately extensive and well-functioning services. The five components assessed were

organization and administration, admissions, guidance programs and services, student assistance programs, and co-curricular programs and activities (PAASCU). Opportunities for improvement include admission policies, counseling programs, services, and community involvement in student activities. The highly rated aspects were health programs, specific policies and regulations, and organization of club activities.

Table 8 The Status of the Diocesan Schools on the Area of Social Orientation and Community Involvement as Assessed by the Parent – Respondents

SOCIAL ORIENTATION AND COMMUNITY INVOLVEMENT	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The relationship between the school and community is one of dynamic.	2.73	Good	2.75	Good	3.5	Very Good	3.23	Good	3.13	Good	3.42	Very Good
The school makes its resources available when needed.	2.6	Good	2.85	Good	3.6	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.62	Very Good
The school plans and implements a continuing community relations program.	2.75	Good	2.81	Good	3.73	Very Good	3.23	Good	3.7	Very Good	3.74	Very Good
The school explores and makes use of the outside community's human, material and technological resources in its instructional program.	2.33	Fair	2.85	Good	3.33	Good	3.73	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.21	Good
The school develops among the members of the school community an awareness of the social issues and deep concern, especially for the poor sectors of the community.	2.73	Good	2.89	Good	3.5	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.4	Very Good	3.9	Very Good
The school provides the entire school community with adequate opportunities to know the conditions and needs of the community	2.5	Fair	3.2	Good	4	Very Good	3.8	Very Good	3.32	Good	3.21	Good
The school renders services to the poor sectors of society by undertaking a school-community awareness and involvement program.	3	Good	3.06	Good	3.76	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.89	Very Good	3.98	Very Good
The school gives financial and/or other forms of assistance to the poor students.	2.76	Good	2.93	Good	3.96	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.34	Good
The school integrates with its curricular and non-curricular programs the students' learning's and experiences from their community involvement activities.	2.96	Good	3.31	Good	3.56	Very Good	3.49	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.87	Very Good
The school provides budget for community-based projects and school-based projects	3	Good	2.85	Good	3.67	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.45	Very Good
Mean Average	2.74	Good	2.95	Good	3.66	Very Good	3.51	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.57	Very Good

As seen in the table, the School of St. Matthias and School of St. Joseph were rated good by the respondents with a mean of 2.74 for the former school and 2.95 for the later. This means that the provision of school orientation and community involvement for both schools were adequate and functioning well.

On the other hand, the School of Our Lady of Atocha had a mean of 3.66, School of St. Joseph the Worker, with a mean of 3.51, the School of St. James the Apostle with a mean 3.54 and school of St. John Berchmans High School, with a mean score of 3.57, was rated very good in this area. This reveals that the provision was moderately extensive and functioned well. To affect the derived formation for students, schools should have a close linkage in the community that could lead to a relationship characterized by mutual service and enrichment. This will somehow guarantee an educational formation that is continuously and effectively responsive to the needs of most Filipino people and the community in general.

Table 9 The Status of the Diocesan Schools on the Area of Organization and Administration as Assessed by the Parent – Respondents

ADMINISTRATION	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The chief executive officer properly delegate authority to and confers frequently with the principal regarding high school matters	3.2	Good	3.45	Very Good	3.95	Very Good	3.84	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	4.21	Exc.
The principal effectively exercises his official functions free from unnecessary pressure and interfere.	3.13	Good	3.16	Good	3.26	Good	3.28	Good	3.25	Good	3.79	Very Good
The principal works harmonically with the chief executive officer and other administrative officials.	3.15	Good	3.16	Good	3.43	Very Good	3.34	Good	3.34	Good	3.55	Very Good
Administrative officers provide effective leadership in carrying out the school philosophy, vision, mission and service to the community	3.57	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.45	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.78	Very Good
The administration oversees the regular updating and upgrading of the school's curriculum.	3.16	Good	3.18	Good	3.78	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.76	Very Good
There is a well-structured and functional supervisory program for classroom instruction.	3.2	Good	3.19	Good	3.68	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3.29	Good	3.65	Very Good
Academic administration ensures the implementation of the schools' philosophy, vision, mission and objectives in the instructional program.	3.26	Good	3.45	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	3.54	Very Good
The administration ensures that on effective grading system in operation	3.56	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.65	Very Good

Faculty and academic non-teaching personnel are provided opportunities to participate in policy formulation and decision-making	3.16	Good	3.43	Very Good	3.79	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.68	Very Good
The non-academic personnel show awareness of and concern for the school's philosophy, vision, mission and objectives.	3.21	Good	3.78	Very Good	3.89	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.78	Very Good
There are existing well-formulated job specifications which are made known to the personnel concerned.	3.43	Very Good	3.87	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.26	Good	3.46	Very Good	3.98	Very Good
The working conditions of the non-academic personnel contribute to their effective performance.	3.23	Good	3.23	Good	3.67	Very Good	3.38	Good	3.53	Very Good	3.62	Very Good
The number of non-academic personnel is adequate to meet the needs of the school.	3.4	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.55	Very Good
Students' applicants are screened through entrance examinations and evaluation of past records.	3.33	Good	3.76	Very Good	3.86	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.19	Good	3.31	Good
Student's applicants are interviewed by the administrative officers (Principals and Guidance Counselor)	3.7	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.71	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3.67	Very Good
There is an officer designated to supervise the financial functions of the institution.	3.36	Good	3.45	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	3.26	Good	3.31	Good
There is adequate and qualified staff to support the execution of financial functions.	3.2	Good	3.78	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.45	Very Good	3.99	Very Good	3.18	Good
All collections are used mainly for the purpose for which they are collected.	3.53	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.28	Good	3.38	Good	3.5	Very Good
The requisition system for purchase of supplies is clearly defined and is functional.	3.43	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.87	Very Good	3.48	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.46	Very Good
There is an operational budget system, and it is properly monitored.	3.45	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.9	Very Good	3.55	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	3.68	Very Good
The key administrators, supervisors and concerned personnel participate in the preparation of the budget.	3.43	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.92	Very Good	3.9	Very Good	3.82	Very Good
There is an annual audit of the schools' books by an external auditor.	3.63	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	4.1	Very Good	3.99	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.68	Very Good
The assets of the school are effectively managed.	3.66	Very Good	3.34	Good	3.98	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	3.89	Very Good	3.31	Good
Records and reports are well kept systematically.	3.23	Good	3.9	Very Good	4.23	Excellent	3.44	Very Good	3.26	Good	3.67	Very Good
All records and reports are systematically documented and filed.	3.43	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.89	Very Good	3.32	Good	3.38	Good	3.31	Good

The principal has a master's degree.	3.6	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.18	Good
The principal implements the schools' objectives and policies.	3.53	Very Good	3.18	Good	4.19	Very Good	3.79	Very Good	3.42	Very Good	3.98	Very Good
Ensure regular evaluation of pupils in the light of the school's objectives and policies.	3.4	Very Good	3.21	Good	3.88	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.38	Good	3.46	Very Good
The principal observes due process in dealing with disciplinary cases and other problem involving pupils/students/faculty/staff/parents.	3.03	Good	3.24	Good	3.78	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.9	Very Good	3.68	Very Good
The parents participate in school projects and activities.	3.56	Very Good	3.14	Good	3.9	Very Good	3.79	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3.25	Good
Mean Average	3.37	Good	3.48	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.59	Very Good

The table shows that five of the Diocesan Schools were rated very good by the respondents with a mean of 3.48 for the school of St. Joseph, 3.78 for the school of Our Lay of Atocha, 3.61 for the School of St. Joseph the Worker, 3.54 for the School of St. James the Apostle and 3.59 for the school of St. John Berchman High School. The computed mean shows that the provision for Administration and Organization is moderately extensive and functioning well.

Organizations and administrations play a vital role in every school. A school should have an administrative organization to facilitate the attainment of its purposes and objectives.

Table 10 presents the assessment of student respondents regarding Purposes and Objectives.

PURPOSES AND OBJECTIVES	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The school's philosophy, vision, and mission are clearly stated.	3.09	Good	3.12	Good	3.41	Very Good	3.2	Good	3.15	Good	3.53	Very Good
The philosophy, vision, mission are reflective of the school's identity and core values.	3.59	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.71	Very Good
The mission statement of the school clearly communicates: A. A culture of excellence	3.18	Good	3.56	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.71	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.93	Very Good
B. Realistic and achievable educational goals for the students.	3.63	Very Good	3.06	Good	3.71	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.81	Very Good
The mission statement deals with the role of the school in: A. The community	3.19	Good	3.89	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.2	Good	3.52	Very Good

B. Realistic and achievable educational goals for the students.	3.63	Very Good	3.06	Good	3.71	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.81	Very Good
The mission statement deals with the role of the school in: A. The community	3.19	Good	3.89	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.2	Good	3.52	Very Good
B. Philippine society	3.59	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.66	Very Good
C. Global society	3.31	Good	3.68	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.71	Very Good	3.41	Very Good
The objectives clearly articulate the school's philosophy, vision, and mission.	3.15	Good	3.87	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.6	Very Good
The objectives are clear, specific and attainable.	3.09	Good	3.12	Good	3.41	Very Good	3.2	Good	3.68	Very Good	3.7	Very Good
The objectives are suited to the clientele which the school intends to serve.	3.59	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.71	Very Good
These objectives are periodically reviewed and updated.	3.18	Good	3.56	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.71	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.67	Very Good
The different sectors of the school are consulted in the review of the philosophy, vision, mission and objectives.	3.63	Very Good	3.06	Good	3.71	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.92	Very Good	3.64	Very Good
The philosophy, vision, and mission, as well as the objectives are published in a bulletin of information.	3.59	Very Good	3.31	Good	3.67	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.71	Very Good
The school includes among its objectives a well-integrated program for the intellectual, moral, social, emotional, spiritual, and physical development of its students.	3.59	Very Good	3.45	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.67	Very Good
The objectives of the school are in accordance with the educational aims of: A. The institution to which it is affiliated	3.63	Very Good	3.09	Good	3.71	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.92	Very Good	3.64	Very Good
B. The department of education.	3.59	Very Good	3.59	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.65	Very Good
The objectives are in consonance with the following rational development goals: A. Patriotism and love of country	3.59	Very Good	3.18	Good	3.64	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.75	Very Good
B. Respect for human rights	3.59	Very Good	3.63	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.84	Very Good	3.53	Very Good
C. Economic self sufficiency	3.63	Very Good	3.59	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.92	Very Good	3.81	Very Good
D. Cultural enrichment	3.75	Very Good	3.59	Very Good	3.41	Very Good	3.2	Good	3.15	Good	3.53	Very Good
E. Social Responsibility	3.31	Good	3.63	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3.71	Very Good
F. Development of moral character and personal discipline	3.43	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	3.79	Very Good	3.8	Very Good	3.96	Very Good	3.9	Very Good

G. Scientific and technological knowledge	3.5	Very Good	3.31	Good	3.56	Very Good	3.58	Very Good	4	Very Good	3.59	Very Good
H. Environmental consciousness and responsibility	3.68	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.84	Very Good	4.23	Excellent	3.9	Very Good
The faculty members and other school personnel understand and accept the schools' philosophy, vision, mission and objectives.	3.31	Good	3.37	Good	3.39	Good	3.4	Very Good	3.38	Good	3.5	Very Good
The faculty and other personnel are informed of the philosophy, vision, mission and objectives of the school.	3.4	Very Good	3.25	Good	3.58	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.42	Very Good	3.68	Very Good
The parents understand and accept the school's philosophy, vision, mission and objectives.	3.81	Very Good	4.06	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	4.19	Very Good	4.6	Excellent
Mean Average	3.47	Very Good	3.48	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.60	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	3.71	Very Good

The table reveals the results of the assessment of the student – respondents around Purposes and Objectives, where all the Diocesan Schools were rated Very Good by the respondents, as shown in the computed mean. The highest computed mean of 3.71 for the School of St. John Berchman High School, 3.68. School of St. James the Apostle, 3.61 for the School of Our Lady of Atocha, 3.60 for the School of St. Joseph the Worker, 3.47 for the School of St. Joseph and 3.47 for the School of St. Matthias. This explains why the provision for this area is moderately extensive and functions well. The vision, mission, goals, and objectives of Diocesan Schools should be reviewed regularly to make it more relevant to the present time and nature of schools. Formulation of schools Philosophy is needed to direct the schools towards the realization of their role in the community as agent of transformation, as evangelizing arm of the local church and to help the country building a just and humane society

Table 11 The Status of the Diocesan Schools on the Area of Faculty as Assessed by the Student – Respondents

FACULTY	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
There is a published policy establishing faculty selection procedures	3.27	Good	3.25	Good	3.45	Very Good	3.16	Good	3.19	Good	3.25	Good
The process of selection includes: A. An evaluation of the applicants' transcript of records and other credentials.	3.12	Good	3.24	Good	3.83	Very Good	3.84	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.5	Very Good
B. Oral writing interviews	3.65	Very Good	3.4	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	4	Very Good	3.33	Good	4	Very Good
C. Qualifying tests	3.77	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	4.05	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.78	Very Good
D. Classroom demonstration	3.63	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.77	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.59	Very Good
E. Consideration of recommendations from reliable sources	3.59	Very Good	3.63	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.56	Very Good

F. Medical examination	3.9	Very Good	3.59	Very Good	4.04	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.9	Very Good
The selection of teachers is a process involving												
A. Principal	3.27	Good	3.9	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.34	Good	3.19	Good	3.25	Good
B. Assistant Principal / Academic in charge	3.81	Very Good	3.27	Good	3.35	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.78	Very Good
C. Subject Area Coordinators	3.14	Good	3.18	Good	3.64	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.5	Very Good
D. Others: Some teachers are involved Human Resource Personnel	3.81	Very Good	3.45	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.71	Very Good
In the selection of faculty members, the following are considered:												
A. Professional competence	3.13	Good	3.81	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	4.04	Very Good	3.07	Good	3.81	Very Good
B. Personality in relation to teaching	3.17	Good	3.27	Good	3.35	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.78	Very Good
The school's specific policies for selection of faculty members are observed.	3.45	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.5	Very Good
The stated procedures for selecting faculty members are satisfactory.	3.45	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.71	Very Good
The procedures of selecting faculty members are consistent	3.18	Good	3.81	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	4.04	Very Good	3.07	Good	3.81	Very Good
The methods in selecting competent faculty member have been successful.	3.8	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.78	Very Good
The percentage of fully qualified members of the faculty is satisfactory.	3.5	Very Good	3.21	Good	3.75	Very Good	3.58	Very Good	3.92	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
The percentage of the faculty members with academic preparation beyond the minimum degree requirements is satisfactory.	3.9	Very Good	3.59	Very Good	4.04	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.9	Very Good
The preparation of the faculty to the requirements of the curriculum is well watched.	3.17	Good	3.23	Good	3.66	Very Good	3.34	Good	3.19	Good	3.25	Good
The total teaching experience of the faculty is satisfactory.	3.21	Good	3.27	Good	3.35	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.78	Very Good
The faculty members' length of service in the school is satisfactory	3.8	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.78	Very Good
There are an adequate number of faculties in relation to the educational program and to the philosophy, vision, mission and objectives of the school.	3.5	Very Good	3.21	Good	3.75	Very Good	3.58	Very Good	3.92	Very Good	3.88	Very Good
Average Mean	3.49	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.55	Very Good	3.68	Very Good

As presented in the table, all Diocesan Schools were rated as Very Good. However, the highest mean was received by St. John Berchmans High School with a mean of 3.68, School of Our Lady of Atocha with a mean of 3.66, School of St. Joseph the Worker with a mean of 3.65, School of St. James the Apostle with a mean of 3.55, School of St. Joseph with a mean of 3.51 and school of St. Matthias with a mean of 3.49. This means that the

provisions/conditions in the faculty's area are moderately extensive and functioning very well. Diocesan Schools were rated Very Good in this area. However, this can be improved to prepare Diocesan Schools for accreditation. Create more activities and programs to enhance the level of competence and competitiveness of faculty and staff for the efficient and effective delivery of services and instruction. Enhanced, competitive, and qualified teachers can contribute significantly to the attainment of the school vision and mission.

Table 12 shows the assessment of the student respondents at the potential level of the Diocesan Schools around the Curricular Programs and Instruction.

CURRICULAR PROGRAMS AND INSTRUCTION	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The curriculum complies the learning competence of the Basic Education Curriculum (Deped)	3.36	Good	4.06	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.35	Good	3.83	Very Good	4.35	Exc.
The curriculum supports the school's philosophy, vision, mission, and objectives.	3.13	Good	3.68	Very Good	3.26	Good	3.78	Very Good	3.36	Good	3.76	Very Good
There is evidence of remote and immediate preparation and thorough planning of instructional activities	3.2	Good	3.68	Very Good	4.12	Very Good	3.4	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.87	Very Good
Instructional activities show systematic organization, implementation and evaluation.	3.13	Good	3.2	Good	4.43	Excellent	3.3	Good	3.98	Very Good	3.43	Very Good
Opportunities are provided for the application of skills/ concepts learned.	3.26	Good	3.18	Good	3.05	Good	3.28	Good	3.56	Very Good	3.43	Very Good
Methods and technique used instruction as varied, current, relevant and creative.	3.53	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.48	Very Good	4.23	Excellent	3.96	Very Good
There is a pertinent use of the medium of Instruction.	3.46	Very Good	3.18	Good	4.35	Exc.	3.31	Good	3.56	Very Good	3.26	Good
Activities are provided to develop leadership and followership ability.	3.4	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	4.33	Exc.	3.46	Very Good	3.96	Very Good
A learning atmosphere is maintained in all classes through sound classroom management.	3.83	Very Good	4.06	Very Good	4.45	Exc.	3.78	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.26	Good
Students participate actively in class.	3.36	Good	3.68	Very Good	3.35	Good	3.98	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	4.35	Exc.
Students accomplish assigned tasks and homework.	3.46	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.76	Very Good
Students show positive values and attitudes in and out of the classroom.	3.46	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.89	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	4.23	Exc.	3.06	Good
Students show ability to apply the skills and knowledge they have learned on the classroom.	3.4	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	4.36	Exc.	3.56	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.26	Good

Examination is couched and returned to the students on time.	3.83	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.36	Good
The grading system is well-defined and reflects the students' performance.	3.36	Good	3.87	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.9	Very Good	3.9	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
The administration has regular supervisory visits to classes and posts an observation conference.	3.13	Good	3.18	Good	3.26	Good	4.2	Exc.	4.2	Exc.	3.33	Good
The administration employs concrete measures to ensure that rules concerning students' class attendance and punctuality are followed.	3.4	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	4.12	Very Good	4.12	Very Good	4.45	Exc.	4.33	Excellent
The administration requires the use of instructional materials, devices and equipment.	3.23	Good	3.56	Very Good	4.43	Excellent	4.2	Excellent	3.63	Very Good	4.5	Excellent
Measured are to ensure the punctuality and regular attendance of faculty members at their schedule of classes.	3.26	Good	3.87	Very Good	3.05	Good	3.89	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.6	Very Good
Records of the daily attendance of students are maintained.	3.53	Very Good	3.37	Good	3.46	Very Good	3.51	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.9	Very Good
Mean Average	3.39	Good	3.60	Very Good	3.80	Very Good	3.70	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.71	Very Good

The table indicates that the five Diocesan Schools in the area received Very Good ratings. The highest mean of 3.80 was awarded to the School of Our Lady of Atocha, followed by the School of St. James the Apostle with a mean of 3.78. St. John Berchmans High School scored a mean of 3.71, the School of St. Joseph the Worker had 3.70, and the School of St. Joseph of Naguilan received 3.60. Conversely, the School of St. Matthias had the lowest mean value (3.38). This suggests that, in schools rated Very Good, faculty provisions and conditions were moderately extensive and operational. However, at the School of St. Matthias, rated good, curriculum provisions were adequate and functioning well. The instruction and curriculum programs received the highest scores during accreditation. Given the respondents' assessment of the Diocesan Schools, improvement is necessary. Schools should enhance their curricula to align with current trends and be more responsive to church and community needs. Instruction should be intensified by integrating holistic and value-oriented activities across all the subject areas.

Table 13 shows the results of the assessment of the student – respondent at the potential level of Diocesan Schools in the area of the library.

LIBRARY	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The library is administered by a qualified and licensed librarian.	2.22	Fair	2.37	Fair	3.48	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.42	Very Good	3.45	Very Good
There is a provision for clerical assistance.	2.31	Fair	2.41	Fair	3.47	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	2.56	Fair	3.37	Good

The number of librarians and clerical assistants is adequate.	2.18	Fair	2.29	Fair	2.37	Fair	3.32	Good	2.33	Fair	3.39	Good
The librarian has faculty status.	2.25	Fair	2.36	Fair	3.89	Very Good	3.38	Good	3.88	Very Good	3.28	Good
The librarian participates regularly in faculty meetings and other faculty committee meetings.	2.17	Fair	2.12	Fair	2.28	Fair	2.26	Fair	3.22	Good	2.45	Fair
Provision is made for the professional growth of the library and AV personnel.	2.45	Fair	2.43	Fair	3.65	Very Good	2.42	Fair	3.46	Very Good	2.32	Fair
The audio-visual or non-print resources are administered by trained audio-visual personnel.	2.16	Fair	2.5	Fair	3.45	Very Good	2.65	Good	3.73	Very Good	2.67	Good
The number of clerical / technical assistant is adequate.	2.31	Fair	2.75	Good	3.78	Very Good	3.45	Very Good	3.18	Good	3.45	Very Good
There is adequate professional preparation of the librarians and other audio-visual personnel.	2.27	Fair	2.31	Fair	3.59	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.84	Very Good	3.9	Very Good
The librarians and audio-visual personnel are professionally updated.	2.45	Fair	2.62	Good	3.84	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.59	Very Good
There is an adequate number of librarians / staffs	2.68	Good	2.31	Fair	3.87	Very Good	3.23	Good	3.84	Very Good	3.84	Very Good
There is an adequate number of audio-visual personnel /or staff.	2.31	Fair	2.31	Fair	3.59	Very Good	3.42	Very Good	3.15	Good	3.87	Very Good
There is a satisfactory participation of the library and audio-visual center personnel in the development of the educational program.	2.4	Fair	2.25	Fair	3.44	Very Good	3.42	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	3.59	Very Good
The school formulates a well-prepared budget for the library and A.V Center	2.12	Fair	2.62	Good	3.42	Very Good	3.24	Good	3.57	Very Good	3.59	Very Good
The librarian participates in the preparation and management of the budget.	2.5	Fair	2.12	Fair	3.42	Very Good	3.14	Good	3.12	Good	3.87	Very Good
There is a systematic record keeping procedure for the library and A.V Center.	2.18	Fair	2.62	Good	3.44	Very Good	3.14	Good	3.42	Very Good	3.34	Good
There is an existing library/ audio-visual program for the school.	2.31	Fair	2.31	Fair	3.65	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.15	Good	3.96	Very Good
There are basic tools and policies for the selection and purchase of print and non-print materials.	2.4	Fair	2.81	Good	3.42	Very Good	3.42	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.71	Very Good
Print and non-print holdings are well balanced.	2.27	Fair	2.18	Fair	3.9	Very Good	3.24	Good	3.19	Good	3.87	Very Good
Collection of print and non-print materials is evaluated regularly.	2.5	Fair	2.68	Good	3.59	Very Good	3.4	Very Good	3.3	Good	3.43	Very Good
Mean Average	2.32	Fair	2.42	Fair	3.48	Very Good	3.22	Good	3.35	Good	3.45	Very Good

The table indicates that the two schools, St. John Berchmans High School (mean = 3.45) and Our Lady of Atocha (mean = 3.48) were rated as Very Good in the library area,

suggesting moderately extensive and functional provisions. Two other schools, St. James the Apostle (mean of 3.65) and St. Joseph the Worker (mean of 3.22), received good ratings, indicating adequate and well-functioning library provisions. Conversely, St. Matthias (mean of 3.32) and St. Joseph (mean of 2.42) were rated Fair, implying limited but functional library provisions. To ensure quality services and support curricular programs, improvements are necessary, including hiring qualified librarians and audiovisual personnel.

Table 14 presents the results of the assessment of the student – respondent on the potential level of the Diocesan Schools around laboratories.

LABORATORIES	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
Laboratories are spacious enough for the different activities	3.23	Good	3.76	Very Good	3.85	Very Good	3.87	Very Good	3.79	Very Good	3.88	Very Good
Laboratories are appropriately designed for each science subject.	3.24	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.87	Very Good	3.72	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.76	Very Good
Laboratories are accessible to students.	3.62	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.36	Good	3.78	Very Good
A separate storage space under lock and key is provided for poisonous chemicals.	3.68	Very Good	3.59	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.65	Very Good
Preventive measures are taken against danger or discomfort from noxious or unpleasant cases.	3.56	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.55	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.45	Very Good
The equipment, tools and supplies are sufficient to enable the students to work in small groups.	3.2	Good	3.87	Very Good	3.97	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.67	Very Good
Trained laboratory assistants or technicians are employed.	3.24	Good	3.43	Very Good	3.9	Very Good	3.45	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.78	Very Good
The laboratory assistant or technician is skilled and capable of doing minor repairs of laboratory apparatus and equipment.	3.9	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.79	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.65	Very Good
Equipment, apparatus and supplies are systematically stored.	3.26	Good	3.59	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	3.58	Very Good
Materials and supplies are properly labeled.	3.19	Good	3.19	Good	3.65	Very Good	3.45	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.57	Very Good
The laboratories are properly maintained.	3.17	Good	3.72	Very Good	3.48	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	3.81	Very Good
A guide for the use of the laboratory is provided to the students, laboratory staff and faculty.	3.26	Good	3.18	Good	3.88	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	4.68	Excel lent	3.88	Very Good
An organized laboratory orientation program is given to all students.	3.22	Good	3.72	Very Good	3.87	Very Good	3.99	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	3.87	Very Good

Resources of the community and environment are utilized in laboratory experiments and activities.	3.19	Good	3.12	Good	3.79	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	3.89	Very Good
Procurement and upgrading of equipment and supplied are done periodically.	3.45	Very Good	3.4	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.49	Very Good	3.88	Very Good
A computer room / laboratory is made available for the computer program.	3.72	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	3.38	Good	3.87	Very Good	3.65	Very Good
The computer room is equipped with enough computers which are properly installed.	3.46	Very Good	3.14	Good	3.81	Very Good	3.85	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	3.69	Very Good
The computer room / laboratory is strategically located.	3.81	Very Good	3.2	Good	3.76	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.77	Very Good
The computer room is well lighted, well-ventilated and well maintained.	3.81	Very Good	3.01	Good	3.66	Very Good	3.37	Good	3.55	Very Good	3.67	Very Good
There are safety provisions in the computer laboratory.	3.59	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.45	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
There is a computer laboratory development program.	3.34	Good	3.67	Very Good	3.95	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.34	Good	3.87	Very Good
Average Mean	3.44	Very Good	3.48	Very Good	3.79	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	3.73	Very Good

The data indicate that all Diocesan Schools received Very Good ratings, with an overall mean of 3.79. The School of Our Lady of Atocha achieved the highest score, followed by St. John Berchmans High School (3.723) St. James the Apostle (3.67), St. Joseph the Worker (3.67), St. Joseph (3.48), and St. Matthias (3.44) with the lowest score. This suggests that the laboratory provisions were reasonably extensive and functional, but there is room for enhancement to achieve excellence and better prepare Diocesan Schools for future accreditation. Improvements should include larger laboratory spaces for diverse student activities, adequate equipment and supplies for small group work, and the employment of trained laboratory assistants for computers, science, and other subject labs. Additionally, comprehensive laboratory orientation programs should be implemented to educate students about the proper use of supplies and equipment. In relation to accreditation and quality education, Anselmo (2024) emphasized the necessity for modern educational environments to embrace technological advancements and pedagogical innovations to meet evolving educational standards. This study examines the impact of these innovations on teaching and learning, which are directly linked to the quality education standards outlined in various accreditation frameworks.

Table 15 The Status of the Diocesan Schools on the Area of Physical Plant and Facilities as Assessed by the Student – Respondents

PHYSICAL PLANT AND FACILITIES	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The campus is accessible to the clientele	3.23	Good	3.81	Very Good	4.23	Exc.	3.98	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.76	Very Good
The size of the campus is adequate to meet the needs of the present school population.	2.77	Good	2.93	Good	3.05	Good	2.44	Fair	3.46	Very Good	3.53	Very Good
The campus is sufficiently free from the pollution	2.72	Good	2.68	Good	2.75	Good	2.56	Fair	3.57	Very Good	3.44	Very Good
There are provisions for future expansion.	2.77	Good	2.62	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.18	Good	3.34	Good	3.34	Good
There is sufficient parking area.	2.27	Fair	2.81	Good	3.01	Good	3.02	Good	3.38	Good	3.12	Good
The buildings are reasonably earthquake and fire resistant.	2.59	Fair	2.93	Good	3.3	Good	3.04	Good	3.8	Very Good	3.59	Very Good
Corridors and stairways are wide enough to ensure easy traffic flow.	2.63	Good	2.87	Good	3.15	Good	2.96	Good	3.5	Very Good	3.43	Very Good
Corridors and stairways are free from obstructions and stored materials.	2.77	Good	2.43	Fair	3.09	Good	3.08	Good	3.34	Good	3.18	Good
The school building design provided wide overhanging leaves for air circulation and for safety reasons.	2.72	Good	2.68	Good	2.83	Good	2.7	Good	2.96	Good	3.4	Very Good
Covered walks protect students during inclement weather.	2.59	Fair	2.62	Good	3.35	Good	3.12	Good	3.11	Good	3.34	Good
Sufficient windows provide adequate lighting.	2.77	Good	2.87	Good	3.28	Good	3.14	Good	3.07	Good	3.15	Good
All classrooms and instruction areas are well ventilated.	2.72	Good	3.06	Good	3.41	Very Good	3.14	Good	3.53	Very Good	3.15	Good
The comfort rooms are well ventilated.	2.77	Good	2.93	Good	3.15	Good	2.96	Good	3.45	Very Good	3.43	Very Good
The water supply is potable and adequate.	2.27	Fair	2.43	Fair	3.09	Good	3.07	Good	3.34	Good	3.18	Good
Drinking water is tested periodically.	2.59	Fair	2.68	Good	2.83	Good	3.57	Very Good	3.12	Good	3.34	Good
Comfort rooms and laboratory facilities are well maintained	2.63	Good	2.62	Good	3.35	Good	3.5	Very Good	3.16	Good	2.96	Good
There is adequate provision for internal and external communication services.	2.77	Good	2.81	Good	3.41	Very Good	3.34	Good	3.08	Good	3.11	Good
Fire and earthquake drills are conducted periodically.	2.77	Good	2.93	Good	3.05	Good	2.44	Fair	2.7	Good	3.07	Good
The various classrooms are functionally planned.	2.72	Good	2.87	Good	2.75	Good	2.56	Fair	3.12	Good	3.53	Very Good
There are provisions for safe entry and waiting in case of emergencies.	2.77	Good	3.06	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.18	Good	2.9	Good	3.45	Very Good
Auditorium /gymnasium / covered court is/are accessible and safe.	2.27	Fair	2.93	Good	3.01	Good	3.02	Good	2.44	Fair	3.34	Good

The canteen is large enough to accommodate the students.	2.59	Fair	3.12	Good	3.46	Very Good	3.04	Good	3.8	Very Good	3.12	Good
A first-aid room / clinic is available	3.54	Very Good	3.12	Good	3.54	Very Good	3.24	Good	3.84	Very Good	3.16	Good
The offices of the key administrators are accessible to all concerned.	2.5	Fair	3.06	Good	3.11	Good	3.1	Good	3.57	Very Good	3.18	Good
A private office is provided for the principal.	2.22	Fair	3.12	Good	3.22	Good	3.06	Good	3.53	Very Good	3.31	Good
Mean Average	2.68	Good	2.88	Good	3.23	Good	3.06	Good	3.06	Good	3.30	Good

Based on the given table, the area of Physical Plant as assessed by the student – respondents for the Diocesan Schools were rated good, as indicated by the mean value of 3.30. Berchmans’ High School being the highest, 3.23 for School of Our Lady of Atocha, 3.06 for and school of St. James the Apostle, 3.06 for the School of St. Joseph the Worker, 2.88 for the School of St. Joseph and 2.68 for the School of St. The Matthias had the lowest values. This implies that the provision for physical plants in Diocesan Schools is adequate and functioning very well.

Table 16 reveals the assessment of the student – respondents around Student Personnel Services in the Diocesan Schools.

STUDENT SERVICES PERSONNEL	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The admission policy is consistent with the philosophy, vision, mission and objective of the school.	3.18	Good	3.18	Good	3.18	Good	3.18	Good	3.92	Very Good	2.56	Fair
The objectives of the guidance program are clearly stated.	2.63	Good	2.62	Good	3.67	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	2.84	Good
Students have easily access to the guidance office.	3.18	Good	2.43	Fair	3.75	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3.86	Very Good
The orientation service program is conducted annually for all students.	2.54	Fair	3.23	Good	3.71	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	2.73	Good	3.69	Very Good
The guidance office maintains cumulative records of each student.	2.4	Fair	2.75	Good	3.49	Very Good	3.18	Good	3.23	Good	3.45	Very Good
The counselor has easy access to the cumulative folders	3.04	Good	2.75	Good	3.58	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	2.57	Fair	3.49	Very Good
The testing and research service has specific objectives.	2.77	Good	3.23	Good	3.34	Good	3.78	Very Good	3.23	Good	3.35	Good
Adequate space is provided for individual and group testing.	2.77	Good	2.81	Good	3.64	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.38	Good	3.56	Very Good

The counseling service is based on a sound framework consistent with the school's philosophy, vision, mission and objectives.	3.18	Good	2.81	Good	3.52	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.26	Good	3.62	Very Good
The counseling procedures are clear and systematic.	2.54	Fair	3.24	Good	3.58	Very Good	3.58	Very Good	2.76	Good	3.67	Very Good
Provisions are made to evaluate the effectiveness of the counseling service.	2.4	Fair	2.43	Fair	3.66	Very Good	3.34	Good	3.58	Very Good	3.5	Very Good
The guidance counselors plan and organize guidance symposia	3.04	Good	3.33	Good	3.86	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.34	Good	3.03	Good
There is a developmental program for career guidance.	2.77	Good	2.75	Good	3.69	Very Good	3.72	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	2.78	Good
The school has an alumni/alumnae association.	2.77	Good	2.75	Good	3.45	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.72	Very Good	2.78	Good
The health program emphasizes both physical and mental health.	1.95	Fair	3.23	Good	3.49	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.53	Very Good
The school has a physician, a nurse and dentist.	2.54	Fair	2.81	Good	3.35	Good	3.32	Good	3.5	Very Good	2.84	Good
Medical and dental check-ups of all students are done annually.	2.86	Good	2.81	Good	3.56	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.32	Good	2.84	Good
Hot meals are available in the school canteen/cafeteria	2.86	Good	3	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.33	Good
Canteen/ cafeteria prices are reasonable.	2.86	Good	3	Good	3.49	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.11	Good	3.45	Very Good
Students' participation in the student activity program is properly recorded/documented.	3.18	Good	2.81	Good	3.5	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	2.96	Good	2.84	Good
Community resources are tapped/utilized to enrich the student activity program.	2.63	Good	3.37	Good	3.55	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.4	Very Good
The school has specific policies and regulations in the organization and grouping of clubs including the activities.	2.68	Good	2.62	Good	3.83	Very Good	3.8	Very Good	2.76	Good	2.65	Good
The school facilitates the availability of transportation to students.	3	Good	3	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.11	Good	3.65	Very Good
A monitoring scheme for student transportation service is observed.	2.86	Good	2.81	Good	3.71	Very Good	3.72	Very Good	2.96	Good	2.84	Good
Community resources are tapped/utilized to enrich the student activity program.	2.68	Good	2.62	Good	3.77	Very Good	3.34	Good	3.11	Good	2.56	Fair
Mean Average	2.77	Good	2.90	Good	3.58	Very Good	3.55	Very Good	3.04	Good	3.20	Good

An overall mean of 3.58 is given by the respondents for the School of Our Lady of Atocha and 3.55. Joseph the Worker which was interpreted as Very Good. This implies that the respondents' assessment of the provision of student personnel services was moderately extensive and functioning well. On the contrary, St. School John Berchmans with a mean of 3.20, School of St. James the Apostle with a mean of 3.04, the School of St. Joseph with a mean of 2.90 and the School of St. Matthias had a mean of 2.77, which was interpreted as good. This implies that the provision of student personnel services for the four schools is adequate and functions well. Student personnel services should complement the institutions' academic programs through well – directed and coordinated programs of students' activities, which assist the students in realizing their capabilities and contribute to their well – rounded development.

Table 17 shows the status of the Diocesan Schools around School Orientation and Community Involvement, as assessed by the student – respondents.

SCHOOL AND COMMUNITY INVOLVEMENT	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The relationship between the school and community is one of dynamic.	3.7	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.89	Very Good	3.26	Good	4	Very Good	4.71	Exc.
The school makes its resources available when needed.	3.4	Very Good	2.75	Good	3.66	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	4.75	Exc.
The school plans and implements a continuing community relations program.	3.62	Very Good	2.81	Good	3.49	Very Good	4.75	Exc.	4.53	Excellent	3.49	Very Good
The school explores and makes use of the outside community's human, material and technological resources in its instructional program.	3.22	Good	2.81	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.49	Very Good	3	Good	3.62	Very Good
The school develops among the members of the school community an awareness of the social issues and deep concern, especially for the poor sectors of the community.	3.68	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.41	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.03	Good	3.41	Very Good
The school provides the entire school community with adequate opportunities to know the conditions and needs of the community	3.18	Good	3.49	Very Good	3.58	Very Good	3.41	Very Good	3.11	Good	3.58	Very Good
The school renders services to the poor sectors of society by undertaking a school-community awareness and involvement program.	3.04	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.22	Good	3.58	Very Good	3.11	Good	3.22	Good

The school gives financial and/or other forms of assistance to the poor students.	3.04	Good	3.41	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.22	Good	3.61	Very Good	3.03	Good
The school integrates with its curricular and non-curricular programs the students' learning's and experiences from their community involvement activities.	3.31	Good	3.81	Very Good	3.49	Very Good	3.03	Good	3.73	Very Good	3.34	Good
The school provides budget for community-based projects and school-based projects	2.95	Good	3.81	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	2.9	Good
Average Mean	3.31	Good	3.40	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3.58	Very Good	3.60	Very Good

Respondents rated five out of six Diocese schools as Very Good, with mean scores ranging from 3.31 to 3.60, indicating moderately extensive and well-functioning school orientation and community involvement. The School of St. Matthias received a rating of 3.31, suggesting adequate provision in this area. As evangelizing the arms of the church, Diocesan Schools should actively participate in community development, fostering social awareness, responsible citizenship, and stewardship of God's creation in students and employees while emphasizing sincerity, honesty, and concern for the marginalized.

Table 18 shows the assessment of the respondents on the status of the Diocesan Schools as to the area of Administration and Organization.

ORGANIZATION AND ADMINISTRATION	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The chief executive officer properly delegate authority to and confers frequently with the principal regarding high school matters	3	Good	3	Good	3.13	Good	3.12	Good	2.96	Good	3	Good
The principal effectively exercises his official functions free from unnecessary pressure and interfere.	3.13	Good	3.12	Good	3.6	Very Good	3.16	Good	3.11	Good	3.15	Good
The principal works harmonically with the chief executive officer and other administrative officials.	3.54	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
Administrative officers provide effective leadership in carrying out the school philosophy, vision, mission and service to the community	3.5	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.47	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.51	Very Good
The administration oversees the regular updating and upgrading of the school's curriculum.	3.51	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.84	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.56	Very Good

There is a well-structured and functional supervisory program for classroom instruction.	3.18	Good	3.53	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.84	Very Good	3.19	Good	3.15	Good
Academic administration ensures the implementation of the schools' philosophy, vision, mission and objectives in the instructional program.	3.22	Good	3.19	Good	3.73	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.11	Good	3.21	Good
The administration ensures that on effective grading system in in operation	3.5	Very Good	3.11	Good	3.98	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.46	Very Good
Faculty and academic non-teaching personnel are provided opportunities to participate in policy formulation and decision-making	3.59	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.94	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
The non-academic personnel show awareness of and concern for the school's philosophy, vision, mission and objectives.	3.81	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	4.12	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.78	Very Good
There are existing well-formulated job specifications which are made known to the personnel concerned.	3.4	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.15	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.4	Very Good
The working conditions of the non-academic personnel contribute to their effective performance.	3.59	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.21	Good	3.86	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.62	Very Good
The number of non-academic personnel is adequate to meet the needs of the school.	3.4	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.4	Very Good
Students' applicants are screened through entrance examinations and evaluation of past records.	3	Good	3.46	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.19	Good	3.31	Good
Students' applicants are interviewed by the administrative officers (Principals and Guidance Counselor)	3.12	Good	3.19	Good	3.78	Very Good	3.16	Good	3.57	Very Good	3.71	Very Good
There is an officer designated to supervise the financial functions of the institution.	3.56	Very Good	3.31	Good	3.4	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	3.26	Good	3.31	Good
There is adequate and qualified staff to support the execution of financial functions.	3.46	Very Good	3.12	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.03	Good	3.18	Good
All collections are used mainly for the purpose for which they are collected.	3.56	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.4	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.38	Good	3.5	Very Good

The requisition system for purchase of supplies is clearly defined and is functional.	3.18	Good	3.37	Good	3.31	Good	3.48	Very Good	3.3	Good	3.46	Very Good
There is an operational budget system, and it is properly monitored.	3.18	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.71	Very Good	3.55	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	3.68	Very Good
The key administrators, supervisors and concerned personnel participate in the preparation of the budget.	3.5	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.55	Very Good	4.2	Excellent	3.9	Very Good	3.82	Very Good
There is an annual audit of the schools' books by an external auditor.	3.62	Very Good	3.85	Very Good	4.18	Very Good	3.92	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.68	Very Good
The assets of the school are effectively managed.	3.81	Very Good	3.25	Good	3.92	Very Good	4.08	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.62	Very Good
Records and reports are well kept systematically.	3.43	Very Good	3.37	Good	4.05	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.26	Good	3.25	Good
All records and reports are systematically documented and filed.	3.56	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.45	Very Good	3.32	Good	3.38	Good	3.46	Very Good
The principal has a master's degree.	3.63	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.32	Good	4.08	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.68	Very Good
The principal implements the schools' objectives and policies.	3.75	Very Good	3.37	Good	4.07	Very Good	3.07	Good	3.42	Very Good	3.46	Very Good
Ensure regular evaluation of pupils in the light of the school's objectives and policies.	3.36	Good	3.68	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	4.12	Very Good	3.38	Good	3.68	Very Good
The principal observes due process in dealing with disciplinary cases and other problems involving pupils/students/faculty/staff /parents.	3	Good	3	Good	4.09	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3	Good	3.62	Very Good
The parents participate in school projects and activities.	3.54	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3.25	Good
Average Mean	3.54	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3.47	Very Good

The table reflects the rating given by the respondents to all Diocesan Schools, which is Very Good, as reflected in the computed mean. 3.98 For the School of St. Joseph the Worker, 3.64 for the School of Our Lady of Atocha, 3.47 for the School of St. John Berchman High School, 3.57. School of St. James the Apostle, 3.54 for the School of St. Matthias and 3.56 for the School of St. Joseph. The respondents' assessment connotes that the school's provision for administration and organization is moderately extensive and functions well. The area of administration is very important to sustain the administrative setup of schools and to experience harmonious relations among personnel and other stakeholders.

Table 19 presents the assessment of the employee respondents in terms of Purpose and Objectives.

PURPOSES AND OBJECTIVES	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The school's philosophy, vision, and mission are clearly stated.	3.09	Good	3.12	Good	3.41	Very Good	3.20	Good	3.15	Good	3.53	Very Good
The philosophy, vision, mission are reflective of the school's identity and core values.	3.59	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.60	Very Good	3.60	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3.71	Very Good
The mission statement of the school clearly communicates: A culture of excellence	3.18	Good	3.56	Very Good	3.70	Very Good	3.71	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.93	Very Good
B. Realistic and achievable educational goals for the students.	3.63	Very Good	3.06	Good	3.71	Very Good	3.70	Very Good	3.92	Very Good	3.81	Very Good
The mission statement deals with the role of the school in:												
A. The community	3.59	Very Good	3.00	Good	3.67	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.65	Very Good
B. Philippine society	3.59	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.75	Very Good
C. Global society	3.31	Good	3.68	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.84	Very Good	3.53	Very Good
The objectives clearly articulate the school's philosophy, vision, and mission.	3.45	Very Good	3.87	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.92	Very Good	3.81	Very Good
The objectives are clear, specific and attainable.	3.50	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	3.62	Very Good
The objectives are suited to the clientele which the school intends to serve.	3.59	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.71	Very Good	3.72	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.62	Very Good
These objectives are periodically reviewed and updated.	3.72	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	3.79	Very Good	3.82	Very Good	4.11	Very Good	3.81	Very Good
The different sectors of the school are consulted in the review of the philosophy, vision, mission and objectives.	3.13	Good	3.43	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.82	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.90	Very Good
The philosophy, vision, and mission, as well as the objectives are published in a bulletin of information.	3.59	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.58	Very Good	3.42	Very Good	3.62	Very Good
The school includes among its objectives a well integrated program for the intellectual, moral, social, emotional, spiritual, and physical development of its students.	3.50	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.47	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.65	Very Good
The objectives of the school are in accordance with the educational aims of:												
A. The institution to which it is affiliated	3.27	Good	3.50	Very Good	3.37	Good	3.38	Good	3.76	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
B. The department of education.	3.22	Good	3.18	Good	3.30	Good	3.28	Good	3.20	Good	3.34	Good
The objectives are in consonance with the following rational development goals:												
A. Patriotism and love of country	3.31	Good	3.50	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.60	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.50	Very Good
B. Respect for human rights	3.45	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	4.00	Very Good	3.81	Very Good
C. Economic self sufficiency	3.59	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
D. Cultural enrichment	3.50	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.83	Very Good	3.84	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3.75	Very Good
E. Social Responsibility	3.28	Good	3.73	Very Good	3.34	Good	3.37	Good	3.84	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
F. Development of moral character and personal discipline	3.77	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	3.79	Very Good	3.80	Very Good	3.96	Very Good	3.90	Very Good

G. Scientific and technological knowledge	3.50	Very Good	3.31	Good	3.56	Very Good	3.58	Very Good	4.00	Very Good	3.59	Very Good
H. Environmental consciousness and responsibility	3.68	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.84	Very Good	4.23	Excellent	3.90	Very Good
The faculty members and other school personnel understand and accept the schools' philosophy, vision, mission and objectives.	3.31	Good	3.37	Good	3.39	Good	3.40	Very Good	3.38	Good	3.50	Very Good
The faculty and other personnel are informed of the philosophy, vision, mission and objectives of the school.	3.40	Very Good	3.25	Good	3.58	Very Good	3.60	Very Good	3.42	Very Good	3.68	Very Good
The parents understand and accept the school's philosophy, vision, mission and objectives.	3.81	Very Good	4.06	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.50	Very Good	4.19	Very Good	4.60	Excellent
Mean Average	3.46	Very Good	3.51	Very Good	3.60	Very Good	3.59	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	3.71	Very Good

The table reveals the results of the assessment of the employee – respondents around purposes and objectives in which all the Diocesan Schools were rated Very Good, with a mean of 3.71. John Berchmans High School, 3.75 School of St. James the Apostle, 3.59 for School of St. Joseph the Worker, 3.60 for the School of Our Lady of Atocha, 3.51 for the School of St. Joseph and 3.46 for the School of St. Matthias. The computed mean reveals that the provision for the area of purposes and objectives in the six diocesan schools is moderately extensive and functions very well.

In the study of Re. Fr. Roseller M. Martinez, (2009), it was mentioned that the review of the mission – vision of the Diocesan Schools was initiated by a lay supervisor. Then in the year 1995, the school communities began going through the process of clarifying, redefining and finding the meaning of the school vision.

In 1998, the school administrator went through a revision process and came up with recommendations to revise, modify, improve, and make the school's vision – mission relevant and responsive to the needs of the times. In 2001, DSO through Supervisor, presented to the Board the formulated vision – mission for critiquing and final editing. The board headed by the former Bishop Most Rev. Sergio L. Utleg., D.D. approved and instructed the DSO to begin disseminating it to schools for proper implementation.

Table 20 presents the assessment of the employee – respondents in the faculty area.

FACULTY	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
There is a published policy establishing faculty selection procedures	3.27	Good	3.25	Good	3.12	Good	3.16	Good	3.19	Good	3.25	Good
The process of selection includes: A. An evaluation of the applicants' transcript of records and other credentials.	3.50	Very Good	3.50	Very Good	3.83	Very Good	3.84	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.50	Very Good
B. Oral writing interviews	4.05	Very Good	4.00	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	4.00	Very Good	4.00	Very Good
C. Qualifying tests	3.77	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.50	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	3.78	Very Good
D. Classroom demonstration	3.63	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3.59	Very Good

E. Consideration of recommendations from reliable sources	3.54	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
F. Medical examination	3.59	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.26	Good	3.26	Good	3.50	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
The selection of teachers is a process involving												
A. Principal	3.90	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.82	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	3.90	Very Good
B. Assistant Principal / Academic in charge	3.72	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.68	Very Good
C. Subject Area Coordinators	3.45	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.47	Very Good	3.48	Very Good	3.16	Good	3.43	Very Good
D. Others: Some teachers are involved Human Resource Personnel	3.68	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.62	Very Good
In the selection of faculty members, the following are considered:												
A. Professional competence	3.86	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.54	Good	4.04	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.81	Very Good
B. Personality in relation to teaching	3.50	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.07	Good	3.66	Very Good	3.38	Good	3.40	Very Good
The school's specific policies for selection of faculty members are observed.	3.59	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
The stated procedures for selecting faculty members are satisfactory.	3.90	Very Good	3.87	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.84	Very Good	3.90	Very Good
The procedures of selecting faculty members are consistent	3.27	Good	3.25	Good	3.98	Very Good	3.34	Good	3.19	Good	3.25	Good
The methods in selecting competent faculty members have been successful.	3.81	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	3.35	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.78	Very Good
The percentage of fully qualified members of the faculty is satisfactory.	3.45	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.50	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.50	Very Good
The percentage of the faculty members with academic preparation beyond the minimum degree requirements is satisfactory.	3.81	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.50	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.71	Very Good
The preparation of the faculty to the requirements of the curriculum is well watched.	3.31	Good	3.31	Good	3.49	Very Good	3.72	Very Good	3.34	Good	3.31	Good
The total teaching experience of the faculty is satisfactory.	4.00	Very Good	4.00	Very Good	3.71	Very Good	3.60	Very Good	3.96	Very Good	4.06	Very Good
The faculty members' length of service in the school is satisfactory	3.80	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.78	Very Good
There are an adequate number of faculties in relation to the educational program and to the philosophy, vision, mission and objectives of the school.	3.50	Very Good	4.06	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	3.58	Very Good	3.92	Very Good	4.09	Very Good
There are an adequate percentage of the faculty members on full-time basis.	3.68	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.62	Very Good
Mean Average	3.64	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.60	Very Good	3.59	Very Good	3.65	Very Good

The results show that the schools were all rated Very Good based on the computed mean of 3.64 for the School of St. Matthias and School of St. Joseph, 3.61 for the School of Our Lady of Atocha, 3.60 for the School of St. Joseph the Worker, 3.59 for the School of St. James the Apostle and 3.65 for the School of St. John Berchman High School, This means that the provision for faculty is moderately extensive and functioning. The table

shows that most of the items in the faculty area were rated Very Good. This implies that the provision or conditions for faculty members are moderately extensive and functional. However, some of the items were rated as good. These are the items on published policy establishing faculty selection procedures, methods in selecting competent faculty members, adequate number of faculty members, and the teaching experience of the faculty.

Table 21 shows the results of the assessment of the employee – respondents in the Diocesan Schools around curricular programs and instruction.

INSTRUCTION	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The curriculum complies the learning competence of the Basic Education Curriculum (Deped)	3.22	Good	3.18	Good	3.33	Good	3.32	Good	3.15	Good	3.18	Good
The curriculum supports the school's philosophy, vision, mission, and objectives.	3.59	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.60	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.62	Very Good
There is evidence of remote and immediate preparation and thorough planning of instructional activities	3.10	Good	3.10	Good	3.28	Good	3.33	Good	3.92	Very Good	4.00	Very Good
Instructional activities show systematic organization, implementation and evaluation.	3.72	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.13	Good	3.50	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.75	Very Good
Opportunities are provided for the application of skills/ concepts learned.	3.72	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.70	Very Good	3.71	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	3.48	Very Good
Methods and technique used instruction as varied, current, relevant and creative.	3.63	Very Good	3.60	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.62	Very Good
There is a pertinent use of the medium of Instruction.	3.59	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.58	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
Activities are provided to develop leadership and followership ability.	2.50	Fair	3.00	Good	3.13	Good	3.11	Good	4.03	Very Good	4.06	Very Good
A learning atmosphere is maintained in all classes through sound classroom management.	3.81	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.83	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.84	Very Good	3.87	Very Good
Students participate actively in class.	3.63	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.71	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.62	Very Good
Students accomplish assigned tasks and homework.	3.72	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.70	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.75	Very Good
Students show positive values and attitudes in and out of the classroom.	3.81	Very Good	3.75	Very Good	3.83	Very Good	3.80	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.68	Very Good
Students show the ability to apply the skills and knowledge they have learned in the classroom.	3.59	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.59	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.50	Very Good
Examination is couched and returned to the students on time.	3.68	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.90	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	3.68	Very Good
The grading system is well-defined and reflects the students' performance.	3.90	Very Good	3.87	Very Good	3.91	Very Good	3.85	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	3.87	Very Good

The administration has regular supervisory visits to classes and posts an observation conference.	3.22	Good	3.18	Good	3.43	Very Good	3.45	Very Good	3.19	Good	3.18	Good
The administration employs concrete measures to ensure that rules concerning students' class attendance and punctuality are followed.	3.77	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.83	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.75	Very Good
The administration requires the use of instructional materials, devices and equipment.	3.54	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.63	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
Measured are to ensure the punctuality and regular attendance of faculty members at their schedule of classes.	3.90	Very Good	3.87	Very Good	3.93	Very Good	3.90	Very Good	3.88	Very Good	3.87	Very Good
Records of the daily attendance of students are maintained.	3.36	Good	3.37	Good	3.40	Very Good	3.38	Good	3.34	Good	3.31	Good
Mean Average	3.55	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.65	Very Good

The table indicates that all Diocesan Schools were rated as Very Good, with a mean score of 3.55. Individually, Matthias scored 3.56, St. Joseph 3.61, Our Lady of Atocha 3.61, St. Joseph the Worker 3.65, St. Joseph Berchmans High School 3.65, and St. James the Apostle 3.65. This suggests that the instructional provision in these schools is moderately extensive and highly functional. Respondents rated several instructional items as good: item 1, compliance with the Basic Foundation Curriculum (DepEd); item 3, evidence of thorough planning and preparation of instructional activities; item 8, activities fostering leadership and followership abilities; and item 16, regular supervisory visits and post-observation conferences by the administration. These ratings indicated that the conditions for these items were adequate and effective. Items rated as Very Good, based on the computed mean, included Item 10, active student participation in class; Item 15, a well-defined grading system reflecting student performance; and Item 12, students exhibiting positive values and attitudes in and out of the classroom. This demonstrates the moderately extensive and functional provisions of these items. Instructional and curricular programs are central to learning and frequently addressed in school operations. The data show adequate instructional strategies and resources that support curriculum objectives. Teachers should adopt technology-aided instruction to meet the accreditation standards for delivering quality education.

Table 22 describes the status of Diocesan Schools as assessed by the respondents around the library.

LIBRARY	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The library is administered by a qualified and licensed librarian.	2.45	Fair	2.37	Fair	2.28	Fair	2.34	Fair	3.42	Very Good	3.21	Good
There is a provision for clerical assistance.	2.54	Fair	2.31	Fair	2.43	Fair	2.4	Fair	3.42	Very Good	3.37	Good
The number of librarians and clerical assistants is adequate.	2.22	Fair	2.18	Fair	2.37	Fair	2.32	Fair	4.15	Very Good	4.03	Very Good
The librarian has faculty status.	2.22	Fair	2.25	Fair	2.39	Fair	2.38	Fair	3.88	Very Good	3.78	Very Good

The librarian participates regularly in faculty meetings and other faculty committee meetings.	2.22	Fair	2.12	Fair	2.28	Fair	2.22	Fair	3.8	Very Good	3.71	Very Good
Provision is made for the professional growth of the library and AV personnel.	2.45	Fair	2.43	Fair	2.45	Fair	2.42	Fair	3.46	Very Good	3.54	Very Good
The audio-visual or non-print resources are administered by trained audio-visual personnel.	2.45	Fair	2.43	Fair	2.32	Fair	2.3	Fair	3.73	Very Good	3.84	Very Good
The number of clerical / technical assistant is adequate.	2.36	Fair	2.75	Good	2.67	Good	2.66	Good	3.88	Very Good	3.87	Very Good
There is an adequate professional preparation of the librarians and other audio-visual personnel.	2.27	Fair	2.31	Fair	2.5	Fair	2.48	Fair	3.84	Very Good	3.9	Very Good
The librarians and audio-visual personnel are professionally updated.	2.45	Fair	2.62	Good	2.56	Fair	2.56	Fair	3.46	Very Good	3.59	Very Good
There is an adequate number of librarians / staffs	2.31	Fair	2.31	Fair	2.64	Good	2.64	Good	3.84	Very Good	3.84	Very Good
There is an adequate number of audio-visual personnel/or staff.	2.5	Fair	2.31	Fair	2.58	Fair	2.56	Fair	4.15	Very Good	3.87	Very Good
There is a satisfactory participation of the library and audio-visual center personnel in the development of the educational program.	2.4	Fair	2.25	Fair	2.83	Good	2.8	Good	3.69	Very Good	3.59	Very Good
The school formulates a well-prepared budget for the library and A.V Center	2.3	Fair	2.62	Good	2.78	Good	2.54	Fair	3.57	Very Good	3.59	Very Good
The librarian participates in the preparation and management of the budget.	2.22	Fair	2.12	Fair	2.77	Good	2.72	Good	4.03	Very Good	3.87	Very Good
There is a systematic record keeping procedure for the library and A.V Center.	2.68	Good	2.62	Good	2.54	Fair	2.54	Fair	3.42	Very Good	3.34	Good
There is an existing library/ audio-visual program for the school.	2.31	Fair	2.31	Fair	2.52	Fair	2.52	Fair	4.15	Very Good	3.96	Very Good
There are basic tools and policies for the selection and purchase of print and non-print materials.	2.4	Fair	2.81	Good	2.52	Fair	2.5	Fair	3.53	Very Good	3.71	Very Good
Print and non-print holdings are well balance.	2.27	Fair	2.18	Fair	2.54	Fair	2.52	Fair	3.96	Very Good	3.87	Very Good
Collection of print and non-print materials is evaluated regularly.	2.5	Fair	2.68	Good	2.54	Fair	2.54	Fair	3.3	Good	3.43	Very Good
Mean Average	2.38	Fair	2.40	Fair	2.53	Fair	2.50	Fair	3.73	Very Good	3.70	Very Good

The table presents the status of Diocesan school libraries based on the computed means. Four schools received fair ratings: Matthias (2.38) and St. Joseph (2.40), Our Lady of Atocha (2.53), and St. Joseph the Worker (2.50). This suggests limited functional library provisions/conditions. The two schools were rated as very good: St. James the Apostle (3.73) and St. John Berchman High School (3.70), indicating moderately extensive but well-functioning library conditions. These findings highlight the need for substantial improvements. Hiring qualified licensed librarians and acquiring relevant learning materials is crucial. Schools should ensure that spacious, sophisticated libraries are equipped with updated resources to provide comprehensive educational experience.

Table 23 presents the assessments of the employees and respondents around the laboratories.

LABORATORY	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
Laboratories are spacious enough for the different activities	2.54	Fair	2.62	Good	2.96	Good	2.32	Fair	2.69	Good	3.37	Good
Laboratories are appropriately designed for each science subject.	2.59	Fair	2.62	Good	3.22	Good	2.72	Good	2.57	Fair	3.5	Very Good
Laboratories are accessible to students.	2.9	Good	3.06	Good	3.03	Good	2.44	Fair	3.15	Good	3.62	Very Good
A separate storage space under lock and key is provided for poisonous chemicals.	2.72	Good	2.75	Good	2.92	Good	2.65	Good	2.65	Good	3.31	Good
Preventive measures are taken against danger or discomfort from noxious or unpleasant cases.	2.81	Good	2.93	Good	2.94	Good	2.98	Good	3.03	Good	2.84	Good
The equipment tools and supplies are sufficient to enable the students to work in small groups.	2.72	Good	2.87	Good	2.64	Good	2.93	Good	2.84	Good	2.75	Good
Trained laboratory assistants or technicians are employed.	2.45	Fair	2.43	Fair	2.67	Good	2.89	Good	2.53	Fair	2.5	Fair
The laboratory assistant or technicians is skilled and capable of doing minor repairs of laboratory apparatus and equipment.	2.9	Good	3.06	Good	2.64	Good	3.65	Very Good	3.11	Good	2.87	Good
Equipment, apparatus and supplies are systematically stored.	2.86	Good	3.06	Good	2.98	Good	2.88	Good	3.11	Good	2.87	Good
Materials and supplies are properly labeled.	2.59	Fair	3.6	Very Good	3.2	Good	3.6	Very Good	2.5	Fair	2.59	Fair
The laboratories are properly maintained.	2.73	Good	3.61	Very Good	2.92	Good	3.69	Very Good	2.96	Good	2.81	Good
A guide for the use of the laboratory is provided to the students, laboratory staff and faculty.	2.86	Good	2.87	Good	3.03	Good	2.46	Fair	2.96	Good	2.87	Good
An organized laboratory orientation program is given you all students.	2.81	Good	2.3	Fair	2.9	Good	2.26	Fair	3.07	Good	2.81	Good
Resources of the community and environment are utilized in laboratory experiments and activities.	2.59	Fair	2.62	Good	3.03	Good	2.78	Good	2.73	Good	2.59	Fair
Procurement and upgrading of equipment and supplied are done periodically.	2.45	Fair	2.62	Good	2.43	Fair	2.6	Good	2.65	Good	2.46	Fair
A computer room / laboratory is made available for the computer program.	2.72	Good	2.68	Good	2.69	Good	2.38	Fair	2.69	Good	2.71	Good

The computer room is equipped with enough computers which are properly installed.	2.9	Good	2.56	Fair	2.81	Good	2.85	Good	3.19	Good	2.9	Good
The computer room / laboratory is strategically located.	2.81	Good	2.3	Fair	2.96	Good	2.88	Good	2.92	Good	2.78	Good
The computer room is well lighted, well-ventilated and well maintained.	2.81	Good	2.01	Fair	3.01	Good	3.2	Good	2.92	Good	2.78	Good
There are safety provisions in the computer laboratory.	2.59	Fair	2.68	Good	2.92	Good	2.68	Good	2.64	Good	2.56	Fair
There is a computer laboratory development program.	3.09	Good	2.85	Good	2.92	Good	2.6	Good	3.34	Good	3.06	Good
Mean Average	2.74	Good	2.78	Good	2.90	Good	2.83	Good	2.86	Good	2.88	Good

As presented in the table, all the Diocesan Schools were rated as good, as shown in the computed mean. This reveals that the provisions and conditions in laboratories in all Diocesan Schools are adequate and functioning well. Garnering with the highest mean is the School of Our Lady of Atocha (2.90), followed by the School of St. Berchmans High School (2.88) followed by the School of St. James the Apostle with 2.86, School of St. Joseph the Worker with 2.83, School of St. Joseph with 2.78 and 2.74 for the School of St. Matthias. During accreditation, the laboratory components that the accreditors were looking into were facilities, equipment and supplies, maintenance, special learning centers and laboratories, and other provisions such as simulations including the play area for indoor and outdoor activities. These are essential parts of the school's curricular programs that can help students attain the course of basic education.

Table 24 reveals that the assessment of the employee – respondents in terms of the Physical Plant and Facilities is adequate and functioning well.

PHYSICAL PLANT	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The campus is accessible to the clientele	2.72	Good	2.37	Fair	3.94	Very Good	3.74	Very Good	2.88	Good	2.78	Good
The size of the campus is adequate to meet the needs of the present school population.	3.27	Good	2.43	Fair	3.34	Good	3.46	Very Good	3.42	Very Good	3.53	Very Good
The campus is sufficiently free from the pollution	2.95	Good	2.12	Fair	3.43	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.11	Good	3.93	Very Good
There are provisions for future expansion.	2.27	Fair	2.31	Fair	2.88	Good	2.98	Good	3.46	Very Good	3.46	Very Good
There is sufficient parking area.	2.77	Good	2.87	Good	3.28	Good	3.14	Good	3.07	Good	3.15	Good
The buildings are reasonably earthquake and fire resistant.	2.31	Fair	2.37	Fair	3.41	Very Good	3.14	Good	3.57	Very Good	3.65	Very Good
Corridors and stairways are wide enough to ensure easy traffic flow.	2.59	Fair	2.62	Good	3.15	Good	2.96	Good	3.5	Very Good	3.43	Very Good
Corridors and stairways are free from obstructions and stored materials.	2.36	Fair	2.43	Fair	3.09	Good	3.08	Good	3.34	Good	3.18	Good

The school building design provided wide overhanging leaves for air circulation and for safety reasons.	3.09	Good	2.68	Good	2.83	Good	2.7	Good	2.96	Good	3.4	Very Good
Covered walks protect students during inclement weather.	2.22	Fair	2.62	Good	3.35	Good	3.12	Good	3.11	Good	3.34	Good
Sufficient windows provide adequate lighting.	2.4	Fair	2.62	Good	2.96	Good	3.04	Good	3.07	Good	3.28	Good
All classrooms and instruction areas are well ventilated.	2.8	Good	2	Fair	3.28	Good	3.04	Good	3.07	Good	3.53	Very Good
The comfort rooms are well ventilated.	2.68	Good	2.68	Good	3.07	Good	2.32	Fair	3.38	Good	3.37	Good
The water supply is potable and adequate.	2.54	Fair	3	Good	3.37	Good	3	Good	3.73	Very Good	3.68	Very Good
Drinking water is tested periodically.	2.63	Good	2.93	Good	2.35	Fair	2.72	Good	3.34	Good	3.31	Good
Comfort rooms and laboratory facilities are well maintained	2.77	Good	2.87	Good	2.71	Good	3	Good	3.07	Good	3.25	Good
There is adequate provision for internal and external communication services.	2.59	Fair	2.81	Good	3.41	Very Good	2.9	Good	3.34	Good	3.31	Good
Fire and earthquake drills are conducted periodically.	2.77	Good	2.93	Good	3.05	Good	2.44	Fair	3.46	Very Good	3.53	Very Good
The various classrooms are functionally planned.	2.72	Good	2.87	Good	2.75	Good	2.56	Fair	3.57	Very Good	4.25	Excellent
There are provisions for safe entry and wait in case of emergencies.	2.77	Good	3.06	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.18	Good	3.34	Good	3.34	Good
Auditorium /gymnasium / covered court is/are accessible and safe.	2.27	Fair	2.93	Good	3.01	Good	3.02	Good	3.38	Good	3.12	Good
The canteen is large enough to accommodate the students.	2.59	Fair	3.12	Good	3.3	Good	3.04	Good	3.8	Very Good	3.59	Very Good
A first-aid room / clinic is available	3.54	Very Good	3.12	Good	3.54	Very Good	3.24	Good	3.84	Very Good	3.16	Good
The offices of the key administrators are accessible to all concerned.	2.5	Fair	3.06	Good	3.11	Good	3.1	Good	3.57	Very Good	3.18	Good
A private office is provided for the principal.	2.22	Fair	3.12	Good	3.22	Good	3.06	Good	3.53	Very Good	3.31	Good
Mean Average	2.65	Good	2.72	Good	3.18	Good	3.03	Good	3.11	Good	3.40	Very Good

The rest of the schools were rated as good, as shown in the computed mean. 3.11 for the School of St. James the Apostle, 3.18 for the School of Our Lady of Atocha, 3.03 for the School of St. Joseph the Worker, 2.72 for the school of St. Joseph and 2.65 for the School of St. Matthias. This reveals that the provisions and conditions surrounding physical plants and facilities are adequate and functioning well. On the contrary, St. John Berchmans High School was rated Very Good in this area, which implies that the provision or condition of Physical Plants and Facilities is moderately extensive and functions very well. Opportunities for improvement in this area were observed based on these data. There are items that were rated fair, meaning the provision is very limited but functioning well among the items are as follows: Item 4, there are provisions for future expansions; Item 6, the buildings are reasonably earthquake and force resistant; Item 14, the water supply is potable and adequate; and Item 21, auditorium/gymnasium/covered court is/are accessible and safe. However, one item was described as excellent by the respondent in

the School of St. John Berchman High School as shown in the mean of 4.25 is item 19. Various classrooms are functionally planned.

Table 25 shows the results of the assessment by the employee respondents around Student Personnel Services.

STUDENT PERSONNEL SERVICES	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The admission policy is consistent with the philosophy, vision, mission and objective of the school.	2.54	Fair	2.56	Fair	3.18	Good	3.18	Good	3.92	Very Good	2.56	Fair
The objectives of the guidance program are clearly stated.	2.86	Good	2.75	Good	3.67	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	2.73	Good	2.84	Good
Students have easily access to the guidance office.	2.86	Good	2.81	Good	3.75	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	2.84	Good
The orientation service program is conducted annually for all students.	2.86	Good	2.75	Good	3.71	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	2.73	Good	3.4	Very Good
The guidance office maintains cumulative records of each student.	3.18	Good	3.18	Good	3.49	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.23	Good	3.81	Very Good
The counselor has easy access to the cumulative folders	2.63	Good	2.56	Fair	3.58	Very Good	3.58	Very Good	2.57	Fair	3.59	Very Good
The testing and research service has specific objectives.	3.18	Good	3.18	Good	3.34	Good	3.34	Good	3.23	Good	3.18	Good
Adequate space is provided for individual and group testing.	2.63	Good	2.56	Fair	3.64	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.38	Good	3.65	Very Good
The counseling service is based on a sound framework consistent with the school's philosophy, vision, mission and objectives.	3.18	Good	3.18	Good	3.52	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	3.26	Good	3.81	Very Good
The counseling procedures are clear and systematic.	2.54	Fair	2.62	Good	3.58	Very Good	3.6	Very Good	2.76	Good	3.67	Very Good
Provisions are made to evaluate the effectiveness of the counseling service.	2.4	Fair	2.43	Fair	3.66	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	2.61	Good	3.5	Very Good
The guidance counselors plan and organize guidance symposia	3.04	Good	3	Good	3.86	Very Good	3.8	Very Good	3.11	Good	3.03	Good
There is a developmental program for career guidance.	2.77	Good	2.75	Good	3.69	Very Good	3.72	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	2.78	Good
The school has an alumni/alumnae association.	2.77	Good	2.75	Good	3.45	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	2.84	Good	2.78	Good
The health program emphasizes both physical and mental health.	1.95	Fair	2	Fair	3.49	Very Good	3.5	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.53	Very Good
The school has a physician, a nurse and dentist.	2.86	Good	2.81	Good	3.35	Good	3.32	Good	2.92	Good	2.84	Good
Medical and dental check-ups of all students are done annually.	2.86	Good	2.81	Good	3.56	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	2.92	Good	2.84	Good
Hot meals are available in the school canteen/cafeteria	3	Good	3	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3	Good
Canteen/ cafeteria prices are reasonable.	3	Good	3	Good	3.49	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.11	Good	3	Good
Students' participation in the student activity program is properly recorded/documentated.	2.86	Good	2.81	Good	3.5	Very Good	3.52	Very Good	2.96	Good	2.84	Good
Community resources are tapped/utilized to enrich the student activity program.	3.4	Very Good	3.37	Good	3.55	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.4	Very Good

The school has specific policies and regulations in the organization and grouping of clubs including the activities.	2.68	Good	2.62	Good	3.83	Very Good	3.8	Very Good	2.76	Good	2.65	Good
The school facilitates the availability of transportation to students.	3	Good	3	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.11	Good	3	Good
A monitoring scheme for student transportation service is observed.	2.86	Good	2.81	Good	3.71	Very Good	3.72	Very Good	2.96	Good	2.84	Good
Community resources are tapped/utilized to enrich the student activity program.	2.68	Good	2.62	Good	3.77	Very Good	3.34	Good	3.11	Good	2.56	Fair
Mean Average	2.82	Good	2.80	Good	3.58	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	2.89	Good	3.11	Good

The output indicates that two schools were described as Very Good along this area, as seen in the computed mean. 3.58 for the School of Our Lady of Atocha and 3.56 for the School of St. Joseph the Worker. This implies that the provisions and conditions of student services in both schools were moderately extensive and functional. On the contrary, St. School Matthias with a mean of 2.82, School of St. James the Apostle with a mean of 2.89 and the School of St. John Berchmanns High School with a mean 3.11 and the School of St. Joseph with a mean of 2.80 were described as Good in this area. This reveals that the provision of student services is adequate and functioning well. Student Personnel Services are vital in the directory of the school and the realization of its purposes and objectives. SPS complements the institutions' academic programs through well – directed and coordinated programs of student activities that assist students in realizing their capabilities. (PAASCU)

Table 26 shows the assessment of the employee – respondents in the potential level of the Diocesan Schools as the area of School Orientation and Community Involvement.

SCHOOL AND COMMUNITY INVOLVEMENT	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The relationship between the school and community is one of dynamic.	2.86	Good	2.75	Good	3.47	Very Good	3.26	Good	4	Very Good	4.71	Exc.
The school makes its resources available when needed.	2.86	Good	2.75	Good	3.67	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	4.75	Exc.
The school plans and implements a continuing community relations program.	2.18	Fair	2.81	Good	4	Very Good	3.82	Very Good	4.53	Excellent	2.56	Fair
The school explores and makes use of the outside community's human, material and technological resources in its instructional program.	3.04	Good	2.81	Good	3.73	Very Good	3.7	Very Good	3	Good	3	Good
The school develops among the members of the school community an awareness of the social issues and deep concern especially for the poor sectors of the community.	2.9	Good	2.87	Good	3.41	Very Good	3.4	Very Good	3.03	Good	2.9	Good
The school provides the entire school community with adequate opportunities to know the conditions and needs of the community	3.18	Good	3.00	Good	3.58	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.11	Good	3.15	Good

The school renders services to the poor sectors of society by undertaking a school-community awareness and involvement program.	3.04	Good	3.06	Good	3.22	Good	3.22	Good	3.11	Good	3.06	Good
The school gives financial and/or other forms of assistance to the poor students.	3.04	Good	2.93	Good	3.66	Very Good	3.68	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.03	Good
The school integrates with its curricular and non-curricular programs the students' learning's and experiences from their community involvement activities.	3.31	Good	2.81	Good	3.49	Very Good	3.48	Very Good	3.73	Very Good	3.34	Good
The school provides budget for community-based projects and school-based projects	2.95	Good	2.81	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	2.9	Good
Mean Average	2.94	Good	2.86	Good	3.59	Very Good	3.55	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.34	Good

The data showed that the two schools received the highest computed mean of 3.55. Joseph the Worker and School of St. James the Apostle of 3.58. The results showed that the respondents gave a rating of Very Good, as interpreted in the computed mean. This means that the school's status in terms of community involvement is moderately extensive and functions well. On the other hand, with a mean of 2.93 for the School of St. Matthias, 3.26 for the School of St. Joseph and 3.34 for the School of St. John Berchmans High School rated the school as good, which means that the school's status in terms of community involvement is adequate and functioning well.

Table 27 presents an assessment of the respondents in the areas of Administration and Organization.

ORGANIZATION AND ADMINISTRATION	SSM		SSJ - N		SOLA		SSJ - E		SSJA		SSJBH	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
The chief executive officer properly delegate authority to and confers frequently with the principal regarding high school matters	3.00	Good	3.00	Good	3.13	Good	3.12	Good	2.96	Good	3.00	Good
The principal effectively exercises his official functions free from unnecessary pressure and interfere.	3.13	Good	3.12	Good	3.60	Very Good	3.16	Good	3.11	Good	3.15	Good
The principal works harmonically with the chief executive officer and other administrative officials.	3.54	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.78	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
Administrative officers provide effective leadership in carrying out the school philosophy, vision, mission and service to the community	3.50	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.47	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.51	Very Good
The administration oversees the regular updating and upgrading of the school's curriculum.	3.51	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.84	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
There is a well-structured and functional supervisory program for classroom instruction.	3.18	Good	3.18	Good	3.60	Very Good	3.84	Very Good	3.19	Good	3.15	Good

Academic administration ensures the implementation of the schools' philosophy, vision, mission and objectives in the instructional program.	3.22	Good	3.18	Good	3.73	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.11	Good	3.21	Good
The administration ensures that on effective grading system in in operation	3.50	Very Good	3.50	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.70	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.46	Very Good
Faculty and academic non-teaching personnel are provided opportunities to participate in policy formulation and decision-making	3.59	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.94	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.61	Very Good	3.56	Very Good
The non-academic personnel show awareness of and concern for the school's philosophy, vision, mission and objectives.	3.81	Very Good	3.81	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	4.12	Very Good	3.76	Very Good	3.78	Very Good
There are existing well-formulated job specifications which are made known to the personnel concerned.	3.40	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	4.09	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.40	Very Good
The working conditions of the non-academic personnel contribute to their effective performance.	3.59	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.86	Very Good	3.53	Very Good	3.62	Very Good
The number of non-academic personnel is adequate to meet the needs of the school.	3.40	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.46	Very Good	3.40	Very Good
Students' applicants are screened through entrance examinations and evaluation of past records.	3.27	Good	3.25	Good	3.84	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.19	Good	3.31	Good
Student's applicants are interviewed by the administrative officers (Principals and Guidance	3.63	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.66	Very Good	3.16	Good	3.57	Very Good	3.71	Very Good
There is an officer designated to supervise the financial functions of the institution.	3.31	Good	3.31	Good	3.17	Good	3.60	Very Good	3.26	Good	3.31	Good
There is adequate and qualified staff to support the execution of financial functions.	3.13	Good	3.12	Good	3.62	Very Good	3.54	Very Good	3.03	Good	3.18	Good
All collections are used mainly for the purpose for which they are collected.	3.50	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.50	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.38	Good	3.50	Very Good
The requisition system for purchase of supplies is clearly defined and is functional.	3.50	Very Good	3.37	Good	3.98	Very Good	3.48	Very Good	3.30	Good	3.46	Very Good
There is an operational budget system, and it is properly monitored.	3.68	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.42	Very Good	3.55	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	3.68	Very Good
The key administrators, supervisors and concerned personnel participate in the preparation of the budget.	3.85	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.55	Very Good	4.20	Excellent	3.90	Very Good	3.82	Very Good
There is an annual audit of the schools' books by an external auditor.	3.63	Very Good	3.85	Very Good	4.18	Very Good	3.92	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.68	Very Good
The assets of the school are effectively managed.	3.59	Very Good	3.25	Good	3.92	Very Good	4.08	Very Good	3.50	Very Good	3.62	Very Good
Records and reports are well kept systematically.	3.22	Good	3.37	Good	4.05	Very Good	3.44	Very Good	3.26	Good	3.25	Good
All records and reports are systematically documented and filed.	3.40	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.45	Very Good	3.32	Good	3.38	Good	3.46	Very Good
The principal has a master's degree.	3.63	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.32	Good	4.08	Very Good	3.65	Very Good	3.68	Very Good
The principal implements the school's objectives and policies.	3.75	Very Good	3.37	Good	4.07	Very Good	3.07	Good	3.42	Very Good	3.46	Very Good

Ensure regular evaluation of pupils in the light of the school's objectives and policies.	3.36	Good	3.68	Very Good	3.67	Very Good	4.12	Very Good	3.38	Good	3.68	Very Good
The principal observes due process in dealing with disciplinary cases and other problem involving pupils/students/faculty/staff/parents.	3.00	Good	3.00	Good	4.09	Very Good	3.62	Very Good	3.00	Good	3.62	Very Good
The parents participate in school's projects and activities.	3.54	Very Good	3.56	Very Good	3.64	Very Good	3.98	Very Good	3.57	Very Good	3.25	Good
Mean Average	3.45	Very Good	3.43	Very Good	3.71	Very Good	3.69	Very Good	3.40	Very Good	3.47	Very Good

The results showed that the respondents in all schools gave a rating of Very Good for their respective schools. The highest mean 3.71 was received by the School of Our Lady of Atocha, followed by the School of St. Joseph the Worker with a mean of 3.69., the School of St. John Berchmans High School, with a mean of 3.477, interpreted as Very Good as well as the School of St. Matthias with a mean of 3.45 and the School of St. Joseph with a mean of 3.43. This implies that schools' status around Administration and Organization is moderately extensive and functioning. The output shows that the respondents recognized the importance of administration and organization in the learning institution.

2. Is there a significant difference in the assessment among the students, parents and employees based on the following areas: Purposes and Objectives, Faculty, Curricular Programs and Instruction, Library, Laboratories, Physical Plant and Facilities, Student Personnel Services, Social Orientation and Community Development and Organization and Administration

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F Computed Value	F Tabular Value	Sig. Level	Decision	Interpretation
Bet. Groups	0.15	2	0.07					
W/in Groups	4.64	24	0.19	0.38	3.40	5%	Accept Ho	Not significant
Total	4.79	26						

Table 28 shows the results of the test of significant differences in the assessment among the parents, employees, and students at the potential level of School of St. Mathias, Inc., Tumauini, Isabela, based on accreditation criteria. The table shows that there was no significant difference in the assessment among the respondents, as evidenced by the computed value of F, which was less than the tabular value of 3.40. This could mean that the assessment of parents, students, and employees with respect to the potential level of the School of St. Matthias using the accreditation criteria were the same.

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F Computed Value	F Tabular Value	Sig. Level	Decision	Interpretation
Bet. Groups	0.12	2	0.06	0.30	3.40	5%	Accept Ho	Not significant
W/in Groups	4.94	24	0.21					
Total	5.06	26						

Table 29 The table reflects the results of the test of significant differences in the assessment among the parents, employees, and students at the potential level of the School of St. Joseph, Inc., Naguillian, Isabela, based on accreditation criteria. It is evident from the results that the computed value of $F > 0.30$ is less than the tabular value of $F = 3.40$. This signifies the acceptance of the null hypothesis, with a significance level of 0.05. This implies that the three groups of respondents did not differ in their assessment.

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F Computed Value	F Tabular Value	Sig. Level	Decision	Interpretation
Bet. Groups	0.25	2	0.13	1.41	3.40	5%	Accept Ho	Not significant
W/in Groups	2.16	24	0.09					
Total	2.41	26						

Table 30 shows the results of the test of significant differences in the assessment among parents, employees, and students at the potential level of the School of Our Lady of Atocha, Inc., Alicia, Isabela, based on the criteria of accreditation. The results showed a computed value of $F = 3.40$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted at a significance level of 0.05. This means that there was no significant difference in the assessment among students, parents, and employees at the potential level of the school.

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F Computed Value	F Tabular Value	Sig. Level	Decision	Interpretation
Bet. Groups	0.17	2	0.08	0.81	3.40	5%	Accept Ho	Not significant
W/in Groups	2.51	24	0.10					
Total	2.68	26						

Table 31 shows the results of the test of significant differences in the assessment among parents, employees, and students at the potential level of the School of St. Joseph the Worker, Inc., Echague, Isabela based on the criteria of accreditation. The results indicate that the computed value of 0.81 is less than the tabular value of 3.40. This signifies the acceptance of the null hypothesis at a significance level of 0.05, indicating that, in general, there is no significant difference in the assessment among respondents regarding the potential level of the school using the criteria of accreditation.

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F Computed Value	F Tabular Value	Sig. Level	Decision	Interpretation
Bet. Groups	0.12	2	0.01					
W/in Groups	2.24	24	0.09	0.10	3.40	5%	Accept Ho	Not significant
Total	2.26	26						

Table 32 Results of the Test of Significant Differences in the Assessment among Parents, Employees, and Students in the Potential Level of the School of St. James the Apostle, Inc., Santiago City Isabela using the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) This reflects the results of the test of significant differences in the assessment among the parents, employees, and students on the potential level of the School of St. James the Apostle, Inc., Santiago City Isabela using the criteria of accreditation. It is evident from the results that the computed value of $F = 0.10$ is less than the tabular value of $F = 3.40$. This signifies the acceptance of the null hypothesis at the significance level of 0.05, that there is no significant difference in the assessment among respondents. This implies that these groups of respondents do not differ in their assessment of the potential level of the school using the criteria of accreditation.

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F Computed Value	F Tabular Value	Sig. Level	Decision	Interpretation
Bet. Groups	0.05	2	0.02					
W/in Groups	1.46	24	0.06	0.40	3.40	5%	Accept Ho	Not significant
Total	1.51	26						

Table 33 shows the results of the test of significant differences in the assessment among parents, employees, and students at the potential level of the School of St. John Berchmans High School, Inc., Cordon, Israel, using the criteria for accreditation. The results show that there was no significant difference in the assessment among the respondents, as evidenced by the computed value of F , which was less than the tabular value of 3.40. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted at a significance level of 0.05. Thus, there was no significant difference in the assessments among the groups of respondents.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the findings, the researcher concluded that there are schools in the IDSS that could possibly apply now for accreditation since the rating given by the respondents ranges from 2.71-4.89 with qualitative descriptions from Fair to Very Good. The identified schools ready for accreditation are the schools of Our Lady of Atocha, Inc., Alicia, Isabela, and School of St. James the Apostle, Inc., Santiago City, and School of St. John Berchmans High School, Inc., Cordon Isabela. However, there are some noted opportunities for improvement that were observed, particularly in the areas of Library, Laboratories, and Physical Plant and Facilities. The results of the assessment made by the three groups of respondents on the potential level of the IDSS schools using the

PAASCU criteria of accreditation could serve as a tool or instrument in identifying their strengths and weaknesses and formulating their Institutional Development Plan.

The result of the test of significant difference in the assessment shows that parents, students, and employees have the same assessment in all areas for accreditation.

Recommendations

Based on these findings and conclusions, the researcher strongly recommends the following:

1. There should be a regular evaluation of the policies, programs, and activities of IDSS schools using or adopting the criteria of accreditation by the PAASCU.
2. Considering the very good assessment gained by the IDSS schools in some of the areas like Administration and Organization, Faculty and Instruction, the schools should likewise give more attention to areas assessed as “Good” or “Fair” e.g. the areas on Library, Laboratories and Physical Plants and Facilities.
3. As fast-growing institutions, the BOT and Administrators should encourage IDSS schools to apply for accreditation so that through this process, schools could determine further improvements that could cater to the growing and changing needs of their clientele and address the demands of the community as a whole. It also gives justice to the demands of the K in the 12 Curriculum.
4. Since religion is the core of the curriculum, schools should intensify the integration of Christian values in all their programs and activities.
5. The immediate implementation of the proposed Institutional Plan for IDSS for improvement and better delivery of Catholic quality education and to prepare the school for the process of accreditation so that the role of the schools as an evangelizing arm of the local church can be realized to the fullest.
6. Some should affirm or confirm the results of the research study by evaluating school curricular programs and activities during planning using the instrument of accreditation by the PAASCU. Alternatively, validation can be performed through an application for accreditation. The researcher also recommends further research to improve this research.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to all ethical guidelines and standards throughout the research process. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from all participants to ensure their voluntary involvement and understanding of the study’s purpose. Confidence and anonymity were strictly maintained, and all data were handled in accordance with ethical research protocols to protect participants' privacy. Additionally, this research was conducted with integrity, transparency, and respect for the rights and dignity of all the

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